

UNIVERSITETET I AGDER

MASTER THESIS IN MENTAL HEALTH CARE

ME 504

THE IMPACT OF SPIRITUALITY IN MENTAL HEALTH CARE

**Literature Review of 10 Scientific Articles about the Spiritual Needs of Patients in Mental
Health Care**

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ABSTRACT

This Master's essay attempts to answer three research questions: (1) Which kinds of spiritual needs do patients experience in mental health care? (2) How do patients experience the relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health? (3) How do patients relate their spiritual needs to their experience of the meaning of their life and suffering? A qualitative research design and a hermeneutic phenomenology method are used in this study. The study reviewed ten scientific articles on spirituality in mental health care as relevant to professional health caregivers. Findings show that patients' spiritual needs could be given a religious meaning (which constitutes patients' participation in religious activities and fellowships), existential meaning (which entails having the transcendence experience and purpose of life), and a holistic meaning of spirituality (which incorporates communal, religious, and existential understanding of spirituality). Patients experience that satisfaction of their spiritual needs helps them to find meaning to their suffering and purpose in their life. Incorporating spiritual intervention in mental health care improved the relationship between patients and healthcare givers, where healthcare givers helped patients to identify spiritual resources to get them through a difficult situation, to cope with suffering, and experience a sense of stability, had a positive impact in patients experience of health. The study concludes that spiritual care is widely neglected in mental health care and that this situation could be corrected by training healthcare givers to be responsive to patients' spiritual needs, which the study proposes as a theme for future research. Thus, to improve patient's health.

Keywords: Spirituality, religion, spiritual needs, meaning, purpose, suffering, health, mental health, wellbeing.

SAMMENDRAG

Denne Masterstudien fokuserer på tre problemstillinger: (1) Hva opplever pasienter i psykisk helsevern som åndelige behov? (2) Hvordan opplever pasienter forholdet mellom tilfredsstillende av sine åndelige behov og forbedring av sin psykiske helse? (3) Hvordan relaterer pasienter seg til sine åndelige behov, i forhold til deres erfaring av meningen med livet og dens lidelse? En kvalitativ forskningsdesign er brukt i studien. Studien har en hermeneutisk fenomenologisk analytisk tilnærming. Studien analyserer ti vitenskapelige artikler om åndelighet innenfor psykisk helse. Den er relevant for alle yrkesgrupper som arbeider i helsesektoren. Resultatene av studien viser at pasientenes åndelige behov kan ha en religiøs betydning (som utgjør pasientenes opplevelse, deltakelse i religiøse aktiviteter og fellesskap), eksistensiell betydning (som innebærer å ha kunnskap om det transsendente eller Gud og opplevelse av mening med ens liv), og en helhetlig forståelse (som omfatter felles, religiøs og eksistensiell forståelse av åndelighet). Pasientene i studien erfarer at tilfredsstillende av sine åndelige behov hjelper dem med å finne mening og formål i livet, tross deres lidelser. Det er vist at pasientens opplevelse av åndelighet har en betydelig positiv innvirkning på deres helse. Integrering av åndelig intervensjon i psykisk helsevern forbedret relasjonen mellom pasienter og helsepersonell, der helsepersonell hjalp pasientene til å identifisere åndelige ressurser. Dette for å få dem til å takle lidelse og oppleve en følelse av stabilitet, til tross for en vanskelig livssituasjon. Studien konkluderer med at åndelig omsorg er svært forsømt i psykisk helsevern, og at dette kan bedres ved å trene helsepersonell i å være lydhøre overfor pasientenes åndelige behov. Funnene i studien kan legge grunnlag for videre forskning, slik at pasienters helse på sikt bedres

Nøkkelord: åndelighet, religion, åndelige behov, mening, hensikt, lidelse, helse, mental helse, velvære.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my late father and my loving mother.

PREFACE

It has been one of my lifelong ambitions to write a project or a book on the impact of spirituality in mental health care to build the notion toward what I feel necessary on the issue of spirituality as regards mental health. I do believe that a constructive criticism from people who have interest in this work is a very welcome attitude that will help the usefulness of this study. I have not positioned myself to mean that people with different ideology, who look at this topic from different perspectives, are on the wrong track, but only derived an academic research to show that knowledge is an infinite horizon which can be built upon. I have argued not to embarrass any religious faith or believe but to distinctively differentiate my position on what I conceive on mental health practise.

I must express my honest appreciation to my supervisor, Professor António Barbosa da Silva (**Dr. theol., Cand. Theol. and Cand. Phil**) for guiding me through, correcting and improving my work and for his constructive critique and encouragement, advice and for leading me throughout the course of study. My appreciation must be extended to Associate Professor Anne Brita Thorød (**Cand.polit. in social work**), whose enormous effort cannot be underestimated and for the encouragement and support rendered to me throughout my study. Enormous gratitude goes to my family members for their concern and contribution to my study. I am also profoundly indebted to all my friends for their special concern and assistance to make my study a reality.

David Adam Braimer, May, 2016.

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CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

In the recent past, the world has witnessed an upsurge in mental health issues among persons of different ages. The ability to cope with mental health issues as well as to ensure the availability of a holistic care system for mental health patients is a matter of great concern (Herrman & Jané-Llopis, 2012). It is important to re-emphasize mental illnesses as medical conditions that disrupt a person's thinking, feelings, mood, ability to communicate to others, and daily functioning (Goldman & Grob, 2003). Just as diabetes is a disorder of the pancreas, mental illnesses are comprised of a group of diseases that frequently result in a diminished competence to cope with ordinary demands of life (Sodestrom & Martinson, 1987).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO 2014),
[...]“*mental health is defined as a state of wellbeing in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to her or his community.*”

According to Anders Johan Wickstrøm Andersen (2006), mental health constitutes of multi-scientific interdisciplinary education and research and field activities geared towards the promotion as well as improvement of people’s mental health. The focus is to ensure that conditions which result in mental health issues are managed by strengthening personal self-worth as well as providing assistance in the process of promoting the ability to cope with daily challenges and ensure the creation of inclusive communities¹. (My translation).

1

Lennart Nordenfelt's theory of health, as cited in Venkatapuram (2013), notes that "health is the ability to achieve vital goals" (Venkatapuram, 2013, p. 271). Mental health and wellbeing are essential to our specific ability as humans to meditate, emote, interrelate with each other, make a living as well as enjoy life. On this premise, the promotion, protection and restoration of mental health can be viewed as an important apprehension of persons, communities and societies all over the world (WHO Media Center, 2014).

Since 1980, there have been a lot of writings on the impact of spirituality in the promotion, protection and restoration of mental health. This study will look into spiritual and existential care impact on mental health (Mazzotti, Mazzuca, Sebastiani, Scoppola, & Marchetti, 2011). To achieve this objective, the study will investigate the patient's needs and experiences of spirituality in mental health care. More specifically, this study aims to develop an understanding of the scope of spiritual needs and how patients experience mental illness. The objective is to find out whether the satisfaction of spiritual needs for patients in mental health care has an impact on their wellbeing (Goldman & Grob, 2003). In order to accomplish this task, some scientific writings will be reviewed to provide an understanding on the role of spirituality and wellbeing in mental health care (Daaleman, Kuckelman, & Frey, 2001; Migdal & MacDonald, 2013; Robbins & Francis, 2000; Steger & Kashdan, 2013; Tsuang et al., 2007). Spiritual and existential care involves caring for the whole person in a human way, i.e. physical, emotional, social, and spiritual (Fagermoen, 2006; Greenstreet, 2006; Kvande, Reidunsdatter, Løhre, Nielsen, & Espnes, 2015; Mazzotti et al., 2011).

Many scholars in mental health care agree that the patients' wellbeing is dependent on their psycho-social state (Stålsett, Austand, Gude, & Martinsen, 2010; Pargament, 1997; Tsuang

See Andersen (2006) especially from page 4 to 15 for insight in mental health.

et al., 2007). According to Stålsett et al. (2010) and Miller (1999), patients receiving mental health care require a balanced mix of both existential and religious dimensions in their treatment to increase their cultural sensitivity towards the treatment process resulting in a differential diagnostic evaluation process. The literature shows that, for there to be any impact on the treatment of patients with mental health issues, the treatment process must be in a position to answer critical existential questions, such as the fear of loneliness occurring due to abandonment and death or life after death (Stålsett et al., 2010; Flannelly et al., 2015).

Stålsett et al.'s (2010) standpoint is in line with the view offered by scholar Yalom (1982), who asserts that human beings face four major existential questions, or concerns in life, which are death, freedom, isolation, and meaninglessness. These concerns give life a harsh tone, but they also provide grounds for developing an understanding of these four existential questions, provide redemption by bringing to the fore the importance of existential psychotherapy (Spinelli, 2006). Existential psychotherapy is a form of psychotherapy with a therapeutic approach focusing on the roots of existence while aiming to increasing the awareness of existential issues in the psychotherapeutic process to raise the chances of recovery for patients receiving mental health care (Yalom, 1982).

According to Hefti (2011), spirituality encompasses a unique dimension of the human beings as it provides meaning to the human life while at the same time forming an essential component of the physician-patient relationship. The literature on the matter continues to indicate that biological, psychological and social factors work together in health and disease. Rather than defining the concept of spirituality as a power beyond description, Sims (1994) advised psychiatrists to view spirituality as consisting of five aspects important to individual wellbeing. The aspects include the search for meaning in life, an emphasis on human solidarity,

an emphasis on individual wholeness (comprising of the mind, body, and spirit), an emphasis on moral aspects of life, and awareness of God (Cranney, 2013; Riley, 1998; Sommer, Baumeister, & Stillman, 2012; Tsuang et al., 2007). Sims (1994) concluded that these aspects of spirituality can act as protective factors for patients, and that having a better understanding of the role that spirituality plays in the lives of patients can help to facilitate their recovery and the promotion of good health (Coyte, Gilbert, & Nicholls, 2007).

Spirituality does not refer primarily to specific religious beliefs and commitment or denominational beliefs. In literature, spirituality is portrayed as the subjective experience of belief with an emphasis on human solidarity as well as the holistic sense of individual wholeness involving the mind, body, and spirit, and an emphasis on moral aspects of life (Hicks & King, 2008; Kahle & Robbins, 2004; Koenig, 2005; Sims, 1994; Hilton, Ghaznavi, & Zuberi, 2002). In addition, spirituality, as a subjective experience of belief, has been linked to a number of positive psychological outcomes (Koenig, 2005; Sims, 1994; Coyte et al., 2007). The outcome includes increased wellbeing, joyfulness, life satisfaction, optimism, reason and significance in life, higher self-esteem, bereavement adaptation, and lower rates of despondency as well as much quicker recovery from despondency (Koenig, 2005; Brown, Hanson, Schmotzer, & Webel, 2014; Błażek, Kaźmierczak, & Besta, 2015).

In relation to this study, spirituality, as suggested by Ellison, is closely related to the question of “meaning and purpose in life” (Ellison, Fang, Flannelly, & Steckler, 2013, p. 215). Spirituality is perceived as the spirit which synthesizes the total personality and provides some sense of energizing direction and order (Ellison et al., 2003). Spirituality is affected by our physical state, feelings, thoughts and relationships. Spirituality also has an effect on the same factors, hence it constitutes an integral part of human fundamental experiences. Given such a

holistic point of view, this study proposes that spiritual care is prerequisite for sound or good mental health care (Nathan, 2004; Tirgari, Iranmanesh, Cheraghi, & Arefi, 2013).

1.2 Presentation of previous research: the state of the art

There is a lot of research literature on spirituality in mental health care both internationally and within the Scandinavian countries (Herrman & Jané-Llopis, 2012).

As noted by Koslander, Barbosa da Silva and Roxberg (2009), ongoing research in mental health has shown the positive effects of the inclusion of a spiritual dimension in mental health care as a means to address patients' spiritual needs as this practice seems to improve the odds of a better outcome in the care process. To integrate spiritual needs in mental health care, health professionals must have a combination of intellectual with a spiritual understanding in their view of mental health care. The above mentioned authors maintain that many existential philosophers, psychiatrists and theologians such as Buber (2002), Frankl (2007), Kierkegaard (2000), May (1993), and Tillich (2000) argue that the existence of the spiritual dimension in the human being is a precondition for the experience of a meaningful life and for mental wellbeing (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009).

Scientific findings and contemporary technology in the West are said to have changed the individual's assessments of spirituality in the study of mental health (Barbosa da Silva, 2002; Holm, 2004; Gallagher, Wadsworth, & Stratton, 2002; McSherry & Ross, 2002; Zinnbauer, Pargament, Cowell, & Scott, 1996). Notably, the existing literature also indicates that older people in a multi-faith society are likely to express their needs for spirituality in a different way (McLaren, 2004; Neno, Aveyard, & Heath, 2007; Schmid & Adami, 2008). According to Koslander and Arvidsson (2007), patients in mental health care have raised questions about the existential and religious dimensions of the human experience. Koslander and Arvidsson (2007)

note that “nursing care encompasses satisfying patients’ socio-cultural, emotional and spiritual existential needs” (Koslander & Arvidsson, 2007, p. 598). They maintain that the studies of Greasley, Chuiu, and Gartland (2001) established that it is necessary that mental health care incorporate spirituality. In their view, they also stress that understanding the value of spirituality must be reintroduced in mental health care and that nursing staff should be attentive to the language of spirituality (Baldacchino, 2008).

Notably, my literature search reveals that some work has been done on the impacts of spirituality on the mental health care context. For example, some of the works include Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg’s (2013) “Existential and Spiritual Needs in Mental Health Care,” Antonovsky’s (1996) “The Salutogenic Model as a Theory to Guide Health Promotion,” Dalmid’s (2006) “Spirituality, Mental Health, Physical Health, and Health-Related Quality of Life Among Women with HIV/AIDS: Integrating Spirituality into Mental Health Care”, and Clarke’s (2010) “Body and Soul in Mental Health Care.”

My presentation of the previous relevant research shows that, although previous studies explore the place of spirituality in mental health care, most studies do not emphasize the understanding of patients’ own perspective on the impact of spirituality on patients’ mental health. This means that *there is a need* for more research and studies to get a specific knowledge of the impact of spirituality in mental health care. This is justification, i.e., *la raison d’être* of this Master’s Essay.

1.3 Research problem

This Master’s Essay is an attempt to solve the following problem:

How patients in mental health care view and experience that the satisfaction of their spiritual needs has an impact on their health and on their experience of the meaning of their lives and sufferings.

1.4 Presentation of three research questions

In order to solve the research problem, the Essay will attempt to answer three main research questions:

1.4.1 Which kinds of spiritual needs do patients experience in mental health care?

1.4.2 How do patients experience the relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health?

1.4.3 How do patients relate their spiritual needs to their experience of the meaning of their life and suffering?

The refinement of the problem

Some technical words will be refined here.

For the sake of clarity in this Essay, the word “spirituality” will be used in three different senses that are, however, closely related to each other:

- α) Spirituality in purely existential sense, designates the meaning of life, true identity (who am I?), purpose of existence, and the meaning of death (Antonovsky, 2012).
- β) Spirituality in religious and especially in biblical sense such as the existence of a higher being (God), nature of God, and God’s will and influence in one’s life (Cranney, 2013; Klinger, 2012).
- χ) Spirituality in a holistic sense, which combines the religious and existential meaning of spirituality (Bush & Bruni, 2008).

The expression “meaning of life” will be used in this essay in the following sense:

- a) Answering of one’s own existential questions/feeling that life is understandable and orderly (Antonovsky, 2012), and that one has a task (Luboshitzky, 2008) or call (Frankl, 2008; Buber, 2002) to fulfill.
- b) Identification of one’s religious responsibilities and expectations (Klinger, 2012).

1.5 Theoretical framework

The main used theory in the essay is based on Antonovsky’s (2012) salutogenic health

model, Frankl's (2003) logotherapy model and philosophical concept, Turbott's (2015) holistic spiritual model, and others that have been used to explore the essence of spiritual care in mental care from a holistic perspective. My study is anchored on concepts that emphasize the role of caregivers, their background, and existential orientation in the ability to attain greater mental as well as physical wellbeing in mental health care patients.

In the process of providing holistic mental health care, the inclusion of spiritual dimension guarantees a broader outlook on the associated symptoms, while paying attention to the underlying issues that cause the mental health symptoms and illness as opposed to merely paying attention to the treatment method only (Turbott, 2015). According to Turbott (2015), the holistic wellbeing of an individual is reliant on their mental health state more so during stressful times. The outcome of mental health care works is dependent on the ability of the patient and caregiver to form a relationship that is beyond the bio-medical treatment and one which pays attention to the patient's spiritual needs (Turbott, 2015). My Master essay is based on the view that a holistic care system that includes both physical and spiritual dimensions of care for individuals undergoing mental health care is an effective approach towards the achievement of effective treatment of mental illnesses. According to the holistic model, health is perceived as the primary concept. This view supports the understanding of spiritual dimension as a core consideration in providing holistic mental health care.

In his salutogenesis theory, Antonovsky (1979) asserts that sound life is a product of an individual's capacity to cope with hardships and to lead a resourceful life by being a positive and proactive individual. Antonovsky's salutogenic model (2012) and Hanson (2007) involves a number of factors that underpin and maintain health and wellness with the key concept being the Sense of Coherence (SOC). Antonovsky describes what he called the SOC as a global orientation

that describes the extent to which an individual possesses a persistent and dynamic level of confidence that:

- “(1) the stimuli that characterize one’s external and internal surroundings are predictable, explicable, and structures;
- (2) the individual has access to resources that can be used to meet the requirements of the stimuli; and
- (3) that these demands presents challenges that are worth engagement and investment” (Antonovsky, 2012).

The salutogenetic health model is anchored on a holistic approach that “expresses the extent to which one has a pervasive, enduring but dynamic confidence that one’s internal and external environment is predictable and follows a specific path” (Antonovsky, 2012). The salutogenic model is constituted by three core components called “comprehensibility,” “manageability,” and “meaningfulness.” Furthermore, Antonovsky indicates that individuals, who have a strong SOC, score high on these three components, as opposed to those people who have a weak SOC (Antonovsky, 2012). “*Comprehendability*” is a concept that designates the degree to which one experiences the stimuli to which he or she is exposed. The ideal is that the stimuli perceived are cognitively understandable, orderly, coherent, and structured with clear information from internal or external environment rather than noisy, chaotic, disorganized, unexpected and incomprehensible stimuli. Comprehensibility is defined as the belief that things happen in an orderly and predictable fashion and a sense that one can understand events in one’s life and reasonably predict what will happen in the future (Antonovsky, 2012). Antonovsky describes *manageability* as a belief that one has the skills or ability, the support, the help, or the resources necessary to take care of things, and those things are manageable and within one’s control. Finally, *meaningfulness* is, according to Antonovsky, the belief that things in life are

interesting and a source of satisfaction, that things are worthwhile and that there is good reason or motive to care about what happens. According to Antonovsky, the third element in the SOC, namely meaningfulness, is the most important. If a person believes that there is no reason to persist, survive and confront challenges, if the person has no sense of meaning, then he/she will have no motivation to comprehend and manage events (Antonovsky, 2012).

Antonovsky's (2012) salutogenetic model is a state of mind, where one has control over resources, or the resources controlled by a legitimate second party, spouse, doctor, God, friend, colleague or someone who is trusted by the individual. Believing in God allows individuals to find, satisfy and report more meaning in their lives (Antonovsky, 2012). Meaningfulness implies participating in one's own life, but most relevant is still the feeling of the meaning, which is more important than the cognitive aspect of the meaning (Antonovsky, 2012). It is about the degree to which one feels that life is understandable emotionally, that one's problems are worth spending strength and focusing ones efforts on (Antonovsky, 2012). Antonovsky is very relevant for this Master Thesis.

Frankl's theory of the searching for meaning of life and suffering is also relevant to this Master essay because it enables me to analyze the connection between the patients' spirituality and their search for the meaning of life and suffering. Frankl holds that patients' spirituality is directly linked to their search of meaning of life and suffering in order to cope with meaninglessness, which is sometimes expressed in the experience of existential vacuum (Frankl, 1966, p. 101; Frankl, 2003). Frankl's (2007) *existence existential or analysis* is described by, Frankl, by means of three keywords: spirit, freedom, and responsibility, and their interrelationship. The ultimate goal of Frankl's existence analysis, i.e., his *Logotherapy* or therapy based on Frankl's (2007) experience, is to help people to be accountable for their

conduct, and be aware that their attitudes can be chosen, despite ambient or context. The foundation on which logotherapy is based is the willingness of the patient to find meaning as well as his/her interpretation of the actual meaning of life. According to Frankl (2003), logotherapy is an existential psychiatric method for treating people with mental disorders by acknowledging the pain that characterizes human existence, like guilt and death. The therapy has an optimistic view of the disorder and how this can lead to growth and thus how despair can be transformed into victory (Batthyany & Levinson, 2009).

Frankl says that there are increasing numbers of patients who express that they have a feeling of emptiness and meaninglessness, which he calls the "existential vacuum." Furthermore, Frankl says that this "vacuum" is a challenge to current psychiatry (Frankl, 2007, p. 11). He agrees that "The psychiatrist can show the patient that life always has a meaning" through the experience of spirituality (Frankl, 2007). Health care cannot show patients "the meaning of life and suffering." However, health care can be instrumental in showing patients the essence of life regardless of their suffering. Additionally, Frankl (2007) emphasizes that a treatment method does not determine the success of therapy, but the interpersonal relationship between the patient and treatment personnel: personal and existential encounter between them.

Coyle (2002), Mazzotti (2011), and Koenig and Cohen (2002) are relevant for my Master Thesis as they provided information about the relationship between tension and its growth into stress, and how this mental strain leads to mental health problems for the individual.

Also Mohr (2006) is relevant as part of the theoretical framework of my Master Thesis, since he investigates nursing involvements in the spiritual domain and claims that spiritual dimensions of care do not exist in spite of the fact that the North American Nursing Diagnosis Association (NANDA) identifies spiritual distress and potential for enhanced spiritual nursing

diagnoses. To the question of what should nurses do with regard to spirituality, Mohr posits that nurses certainly should approach patients holistically as beings that are more than the sum of their parts. According to some studies too, (Narayanasamy & Owens, 2001; Swinton & Narayanasamy, 2002), nurses should recognize and respect patients' spiritual lives, and should continuously focus on patient-center interventions approach (Narayanasamy & Owens, 2001). Thoits (2012) further discusses the importance of having caregivers who understand the essence of applying existential information in the psychotherapeutic process. According to their research, the therapists' background and existential orientation influenced their philosophy of therapeutic practice. These two scholars argue that through increasing the use of the existential dimension in the therapeutic process, the chances of recovery are much higher since the patient has access to information on existential issues that will bring meaning and purpose to their lives. This is in agreement with Thoits (2012), who asserts that the belief that one's life is purposeful and has meaning can yield greater mental as well as physical wellbeing (Thoits, p. 362). The theoretical framework presented here will be used in the analysis of the ten selected articles given in chapters 2, 3 and 4.

1.6 Method of the analysis: hermeneutic phenomenology

1.6.1 The hermeneutic circle and the role of the interpreter's pre-understanding in interpreting a text

Hermeneutics, which delineates the principles and philosophy of interpretation, typically applied in the interpretation of wisdom literature, philosophical texts, and biblical materials (Hummelvoll & Barbosa da Silva, 1998) was used in reviewing ten studies on the impact of spirituality on mental health care. Hermeneutics is used to interpret oral, non-verbal, and written communication.

Phenomenology consists in the study of frameworks of consciousness as experienced

from the *first-person viewpoint*. The core element of the experience lies in its intentionality and direction towards something, that is, an experience about something.

(Hummelvoll & Barbosa da Silva, 1998).

The combination of the two methods (hermeneutics and phenomenology) was deemed important in comprehending the full spiritual experience of mental health care patients. For instance, the phenomenological interpretation and description were deployed to reach patients' spiritual experience from a personal point of view (Hummelvoll & Barbosa da Silva, 1998). This was attained initially through the understanding of phenomena (experiences) under study, such as the spiritual experiences of mental health care patients. Here I have to assume that the authors of the ten articles had given a correct account of the patients' and caregivers' experience (*opplevelse*). The hermeneutic-phenomenological interpretation approach was also used to enable the researcher to provide objective descriptions of the relationship between the satisfaction of patients' spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health (Gadamer, 1960; 1998). Such descriptions presupposed that the authors of the ten articles under review were given an objective, correct account of the participants in their studies.

1.6.2 The concept of the first person, i.e., the phenomenological perspective

Concerning the purpose of this Master Essay, as Hummelvoll and Barbosa da Silva (2013) proposes, a nurse must relate patients to their respective social networks (all networks that they belong) to understand them. This understanding requires a multidirectional understanding of the human being, such as the existential-humanistic view (Hummelvoll & Barbosa da Silva, 2013p. 459). The meaning of suffering and pain also has to be understood from the patient's perspective (the phenomenological viewpoint) (Hummelvoll & Barbosa da Silva, 2013). The meaning experienced by the patient is derived from the patient's knowledge of the

disease and the impacts of his belief on how he/she experiences the illness. Hummelvoll and Barbosa da Silva argue that execution of the power of empathy and experiencing the patient to the farthest point possible and without preconceived ideas must form the foundation of the method that nurses should apply to understand how patients experience illness (Hummelvoll & Barbosa da Silva, 2013, p. 460).

The choice of hermeneutic phenomenology as the method for this study is based on the aim to obtain several benefits from its use (Kafle, 2011). The method allows the researcher to interpret the concealed meanings in the *phenomenon* under the study (Walding, Muir-Cochrane, & May, 2006). In this study the phenomenon is the patients' experiences (*opplevelser*) as described in the ten selected articles reviewed in chapter 2, 3 and 4 below. Hermeneutic phenomenology method is a rigorous, critical and systematic investigation of different phenomena (Crist & Tanner, 2003). As such, hermeneutic phenomenology is in line with the purpose of this study which is to offer rigorous literature reviews (Kafle, 2011).

The phenomenological study allows the researchers to use systematic methods in studying the structure of the phenomena that seem to influence consciousness (Gadamer, 1960; 1998).

1.6.3 Multiple search strategies

When conducting a literature review, it is paramount that the researcher is able to yield the most comprehensive number of articles that can be sourced from the search of literature. The quality of a literature review type of research is highly dependent on the number and quality of articles that are obtained from the search of literature (Cronin, Ryan, & Coughlan, 2008). As such, it is paramount that a researcher uses varied methods to search for the articles to be included in the literature review. For example, the researcher needs to search from different

databases, use different combinations of terms and filter the articles obtained in a thorough manner to ensure that quality articles are obtained for the research (Onwuegbuzie, Leech, & Collins, 2012).

The different searches yielded different number of articles as indicated in the appendix section (Appendix 4).

1.6.4 Selection procedure

Phrases such as ‘spirituality and mental health care,’ ‘patient’s spiritual need in mental health care,’ ‘meaning of life and suffering in mental care,’ ‘meaning of life and suffering in mental health,’ ‘spiritual need and salutogenetic needs,’ ‘the impact of spirituality in mental health care,’ were used because of their relevance to the three research questions of this study. These research terms were deemed justifiable bearing in mind their open structure, which guaranteed a rich yield of articles dealing with the relationship between spirituality and mental health care, articles within health care in general but especially those about cancer patients dealing with mental health care were also integrated in the search and study process.

From the information contained in the titles of the research, the first selection left the researcher with a total of 160 articles after employing the inclusion criteria. The 160 articles sourced from diverse databases including Pub Med, Ovid, EBSCO, Cochran, APA Psyc Net, and Oria. Each of the databases was selected after confirming their inclusion of relevant, quality, and reliable articles. The second level of the search was further refined using the abstract of articles in order to eliminate the non-relevant articles, yielding a total of 93 papers. The third selection was aimed at reducing the number of the articles selected through evaluating the information contained in the introduction and the results section to determine whether the outcome is in line with the aim of the research, a process that yielded 30 articles. The researcher read in full all the

30 articles with the papers that did not match the inclusion criteria and were eliminated. This step also involved looking at the connection between the article's research questions, the methods used in the article's research and the results, discussion and conclusion of the article. Articles that met the inclusion-exclusion criteria while also conforming to the needs of this study, which is to understand the impact of spirituality in mental health care, were chosen. The procedure ended with ten selected articles that met all the inclusion criteria.

The 10 articles were selected because they explored the essence of spirituality in the care of patients suffering from diverse psychological disorders. More importantly, studies on cancer patients were included as they involved people experiencing the end stage of life, a phase that is often accompanied with different psychological issues including stress, hopelessness, anxiety, and uncertainty (Coyte, Gilbert, & Nicholls, 2007). These articles were also chosen because they satisfied all the three provisions of my inclusion criteria.

1.6.5 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

First, the *inclusion* criteria in this study consist of whether an article employs relevant qualitative scientific designs (including hermeneutical approach, phenomenology, and literature review) in line with systematic research standards. Second, the article to be selected had to be published in the period from 1993 to 2015. Third, they must be international articles published in English language. And lastly, the major focus of the selection is articles with content spirituality and mental health care.

Articles with two or three of the key words (see section 1.6.4) in their titles have a better applicability for this paper and are highly ranked in the inclusion criteria (Rau, 2004). However, the researcher had to put in mind the need for sources covering each of these keywords, therefore, once an article satisfied two or three keywords, it was included while other articles

with the same keywords in their titles were excluded. The limitation of the articles to the dates given also allowed the researcher to ensure that the review used a reasonable number of recent relevant writings for the study.

For the *exclusion* criteria, the title was the first instrument used for the selection of articles. Articles with titles that did not reflect this paper's research question were excluded (Burns & Grove, 2001). Articles with a single or no keyword forming the key phrases chosen were also excluded. The exclusion criteria also made use of the date of publication, where articles older than the year 1993 were excluded to ensure that research was up-to-date. Papers using languages other than English were excluded during the process.

1.7 Systematic analysis of the reviewed articles (CASP)

The Critical Appraisal Skills Program (CASP) was used to provide a guide that is the basis for the systematic analysis of the material to ensure that the papers used in the review are of high scientific research standards. The process will include examining each paper to find out how patients experience the satisfaction of their spiritual and existential needs in mental health care. The results will be examined and analysis of the results will be presented under the summary of findings. Presentation of the studies included in the review will be tabulated in Appendix 2.

1.7.1 Own role as a researcher (pre-understanding of the research)

My pre-understanding in this study can be summarized as follows.

The role of the researcher is limited to reporting information contained in the reviewed articles, and the researcher tried to avoid providing his own individual interpretation on the matter under study (Kafle, 2011). As an interpreter I avoided biased reporting by engaging full exploration of arguments in each material my objective in interpreting the 10 articles was also to ensure that the research stimulates intellectual discourses that will eventually contribute towards

the growth of the body of knowledge related to this study (cf. Vinch & Lyman, 2000). It is also important to consider that I am a believer, and this, is bound to influence my religious understanding of spirituality. However, I am committed to maintain an objective view of spirituality by exploring its three meanings (see section 1.4.3) and maintaining an open mind in the conceptualization of spirituality as a concept that is beyond the institutional constraints of one religion. In order to avoid being biased by his/her pre-understanding (what Gadamer calls prejudices) the research aims to provide a thorough understanding of the matter and hence, the researcher has to ensure that only quality articles are included in the review (Crist & Tanner, 2003).

1.8 Presentation of the selected articles

Section 1.8 presents the articles that were reviewed in my study.

1.8.1 Patients' conceptions of how the spiritual dimension is addressed in mental health care: a qualitative study - Koslander & Arvidsson (2007).

This study describes patients' conception of how the spiritual dimension is addressed in mental health care. The study examines the concept of spirituality and religion in their broader perception. The study rehearses the positive effect of spirituality and spiritual values in the context of nursing. The findings sheds light on three themes: patients wish to see their spiritual needs addressed, patients lack confidence in nurses regarding spirituality and finally patients had actively sought nurses' assistance to meet their spiritual needs.

1.8.2 Integrating religion and spirituality into mental health care, psychiatry and psychotherapy - Hefti (2011).

This study examines the integration of spirituality into mental health care, and highlights its controversial roll, the study has a qualitative methodology with integrative approach, it stress out the evidence of the beneficial effects of spirituality and the need for an active and effective

integration of spirituality into mental care. Result shows that religion may help patients to cope with emotional stress and gives hope, purpose and meaning in life. Patients maintained that to have a purpose beyond one's self can make it possible to deal with hardship in life. This study indicate that psychotherapy for spiritual patients can be possible by integrating spiritual elements into the therapy protocol and that can be successfully done by spiritual and non-spiritual therapists.

1.8.3 Religious involvement, spirituality and personal meaning for life: Existential predictors of psychological wellbeing in community-residing and institutional care elders - Fry (2000).

This study examines the influential role of existential factors such as religiosity, spirituality and personal meaning and the mental health wellbeing of older adults. Using hierarchical regression analyses, the results showed that personal meaning, involvement in formal religion, participation in spiritual practices, importance of spirituality, gives a degree of comfort derived from religion, sense of inner peace with self, and accessibility to religious resources were significant predictors of wellbeing for the combined sample. The study showed a pattern of associations between wellbeing and the psychosocial dimensions and spirituality.

1.8.4 Existential and spiritual needs in mental health care: an ethical and holistic perspective – Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009).

This study examines the relationship between existential and spiritual needs with a focus on ethics in health care and patients' mental health wellbeing. The study discusses whether or not patients' needs are holistically taken in consideration in Western health care organizations. Upon analyzing the paper, it is possible to find out that patients' spiritual needs in mental health care are important for patients' improvement and recovery. The study, for example, asserts that for some patients, this is the only way to regain their mental health.

1.8.5 Spiritual coping strategies: a review of the nursing research literature - Baldacchino and Draper (2001).

This study is based on qualitative analysis, with a literature review, it investigates some nursing research papers, within the context of spiritual and the coping strategies used by ill patients, the purpose of this paper is to identify some of the spiritual coping strategies used by the believers and non-believers followed by some suggestions for holistic nursing care.

1.8.6 Body and soul in mental health care - Clarke (2010).

This study is a literature review and presents the concept of body, soul and spirit, it suggest that a holistic comprehension of the person as whole which paraphrases how body and spirit can interact offers an expansion of our understanding of spiritual care, which offers an broader perspective of mental health and the spirituality of patients.

1.8.7 Treading lightly: spirituality issues in mental health nursing – Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006).

This study provides an understanding spirituality by answering a primary research question, ‘What does spirituality mean for people with a mental illness?’ Participants were interviewed and data analyzed using an iterative approach. Results of the study stress out that spirituality is important especially during mental health illness.

1.8.8 Exploring the spiritual meaning of suffering: a strategy of self-help, recovery, and hope - Luboshitzky (2008).

This study examines the sense of suffering from the spiritual mindset of anthroposophy, which perceives suffering as a strong force for achieving the inner wisdom needed for change and transformation. Using an explanatory design, the research presents the theory of recovery-oriented setups, which highlights healing through empowerment, self-help, and transformation.

1.8.9 Assessing a patient's spiritual needs: a comprehensive instrument- Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005).

Seven principle constructs- meaning, belonging, hope, morality, the sacred, acceptance, and beauty of dying-were exposed in an examination of the literature concerning the spiritual needs of mental health care patients. Galek, Flannelly, and Galek based the constructs within a 29-article survey method to be inclusive of conventional religion, as well as non-institutional-oriented spirituality. This article explores the generation of a multidimensional tool designed to evaluate spiritual needs of mental health care patients. This construct for understanding the spiritual needs of patients hopefully contributes to the developing body of literature, providing a blue print for healthcare professionals who are interested in a more comprehensive approach to patient well-being.

1.8.10 Spiritual care as a dimension of holistic care: a relational interpretation- Bush and Bruni (2008).

The article gives an account on a phenomenological study carried out to investigate the meaning of spiritual care as perceived by a group of palliative care practitioners. The study process was based on van Manen's (1990) hermeneutic phenomenological method. Eight palliative care practitioners (nurses, pastoral carers, and complementary therapists) were drawn from a community palliative care organization in Melbourne, Victoria, which offered home-based palliative care. Each participant was female and the group was drawn from diverse ethnic backgrounds. Data were gathered by in-depth interviews and were evaluated thematically. Two themes came up: 'a world of relationships' and 'a living nexus between spirituality, spiritual care, and holism.' The results of the study show the need for healthcare practitioners to incorporate spiritual care procedure into practice to ensure that palliative care represents holistic health care.

A tabulated list of the articles is provided in the appendices section of the research (Appendix 1).

1.9 Validity and reliability

I sought to provide an understanding of the impact of spirituality on mental health care in order to provide the conclusion on the subject matter. As such, the validity of the study was attained by employing phenomenological hermeneutics as interpretative tool in the literature review, i.e., in reviewing the ten articles on the subject and by evaluating how these articles tackle the phenomena of my study (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001). In addition, I attempted to test the the reliability of the results of reviewed studies by using articles that are in line with the topic of this study, which is according to Rau's and Burn and Groove's advice (Rau, 2004; Burns & Groove, 2001). I also discussed my interpretation of the articles with my tutor, to a void being too subjectivist.

1.10 The analysis procedure

The ten reviewed articles were analyzed by investigating the relationship between my research problem of my Master Thesis and my three research questions. The reviewed articles were selected after evaluating whether their content could be used to answer my three research questions or not. The utilization of variable phrases in the search of literature, such as "meaning of life", leads to an article being regarded as more reliable as opposed to an article that employs a single or limited number of search phrases (Burns & Groove, 2001). Though somewhat salient, a close evaluation of the contents of selected articles enabled the me to classify them into three groups .i.e., (1) those that give spirituality an existential meaning, (2) those that give spirituality a religious meaning, and (3) those that give spirituality an holistic meaning (both spiritual and religious meanings) (see chapter 1).

In the literature review I have used the hermeneutic-phenomenological method as follows. For answering my research questions, I have read each of my ten selected article in order to see whether my classification of spirituality in three groups of meaning (religious, existential and holistic) was correct. This analysis is presented in chapter 2. For chapter 3, I have used the selected articles to answer question No. 2 of my Master Thesis, by reading all articles and comparing them with one another, in order to find how to answer my research question no 2 in light of them. I found out that the selected articles were relevant to my study and gave a clear answer to my research question, also here it was relevant to take into consideration my classification of spirituality presented in chapter 2 (religious, existential, and holistic meaning). This made it possible for me to classify my ten selected articles in 3 groups with respect to how the articles describe the relationship between the satisfaction of patients spiritual needs and their experience of the improvement of their health. I also found that some patients had experienced meaning of their life and suffering in light of their religiosity, some other experienced meaning of their suffering in light of their non-religious view of life, and that implies an existential view of life, another group of patients experienced meaning in holistic view of life, which comprises both religious and an existential view of life.

To experience meaning in a context is a fundamental principle in hermeneutics, and for chapter 4 I have answered research question No.3 of my Master study. I have used the hermeneutic circle in the following way: I tried to find how the authors of my selected articles described the experience of the patients spirituality, that is to say, where they do it from the first person point of view (which is called the phenomenological perspective), or scientific objective perspective (which is called the third person point of view). Here I presupposed that the authors

have described the patients experience of spirituality in correct way.(to describe an experience - *opplevelse* - correctly is a phenomenological method)

I have used the hermeneutic circle to interpret how patients in mental health care view and experience that the satisfaction of their spiritual needs has an impact on their health and on their experience of the meaning of their lives (Crist & Tanner, 2003; Ajjawi & Higgs, 2007). The hermeneutic circle affirms that meaning is understood or discovered in a context. The context here is mental health care as a whole and patients' spirituality.

In my use of hermeneutics – as a method of interpretation – I have also reflected on how my preunderstanding could have influenced my interpretation and analysis of the texts (the ten selected articles) and applied this knowledge in fostering unbiased reporting (see discussion chapter 5). By being aware of my own faith, I have tried to be as neutral as possible in searching in the ten articles what is really the patients', the care givers' opinion, and that of the authors of the ten articles.

1.11 Ethical considerations of the research

Given that the sources used are already published, the researcher did not apply to the Faculty Ethical Committees (FEK) to find out if the project needs their approval. On the other hand, there was no need to seek the approval as the research did not involve any harm to any patients because the sources of my study are already published. The researcher also ensures that general guidelines for the conducting systematic reviews are followed, which includes the application of proper referencing techniques to ensure that credit is given to the respective authors of the articles included in the review (Rau, 2004; Burns & Groove, 2001).

1.12 Disposition

The task in this essay follows the following steps: chapter one is the introduction which contains the background (with the description of the aim of study), research problem, and theoretical perspective, presentation of previous research, disposition, and methods. Chapter two, three and four will focus on the three research questions in a specific order. To begin with, chapter two will answer research question No. 1 (see section 1.4.1). In chapter three, the researcher will seek to answer the questions No. 2 (see section 1.4.2) while chapter four will address research question No. 3 (see section 1.4.3). Chapter 5 compares the findings of my study in relationship with those of concerning the relationship between spirituality and mental health care. Chapter 5 also includes the summary of findings, discussion of the findings, conclusion and recommendations, and suggestions for further research.

2. CHAPTER TWO: Which kinds of spiritual needs do patients experience in mental health care?

2.1 Introductory remark

This chapter responds to research question No. 1 (see section 1.4.1). The selected articles have been classified into three groups - those that take a religious meaning in defining the spiritual needs that patients experienced, those that take an existential meaning in exploring patients' spiritual needs, and those that combine religious meaning with the existential meaning in describing spiritual needs, according to the patients' experience respectively. The use of these three different perspectives is supported by the following study.

Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009) mention that spiritual needs are the need for deliverance from despair, guilt, and sin. Further, in their article, Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg classify spiritual needs as belonging to the class of secondary human needs. Secondary human needs include the experience of security and friendship, belonging and acceptance. From this classification, spiritual needs are seen as not being physical, even though they play a role in the physical wellbeing of an individual. Further, Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg affirm that spirituality is a broad concept that is multivalent, highly subjective and hard to define. Some of the spiritual needs that stem from this description include the need for purpose and meaning in/of life, the need to feel useful, the need for hope and the need for recognition of and respect for personal dignity (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009).

In order to properly answer the research question No. 1 of this master's study (see the title of this chapter), this chapter has been divided into the following subsections: (2.2) Spiritual needs as religious needs, (2.3) Spiritual needs as existential needs, and (2.4) Spiritual needs seen from a holistic view of life. The subsection 2.4 is a combination of the subsections 2.2 and 2.3,

i.e., what is called here the *holistic* meaning or sense of the expression “spiritual needs”.

2.2 Spiritual needs as religious needs

Fry’s (2000) article asserts that wholeness can be attained in one’s life when both existential and religious needs have been given due attention. Fry argues that seeking wholeness is the solitary approach to create a sense of personal meaning and that through fulfilling such needs, a person can affirm his or her psychological wellbeing. He concludes that findings show that people who perceive life as being meaningful and have close communion with God, as well as with the inner self, have better chances of having a positive outlook towards life, which keeps them from the vulnerability of depression (Fry, 2000, p. 376). In Fry’s (2000) statement, God, inner peace, and purpose in life emerge as forms of spiritual needs.

The spiritual need is understood as finding a higher being and gaining a higher understanding of what is described in Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006) article as the ‘understanding of being’ (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 145), and seems to be closely related to the spiritual need for God. Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006), in their interview, demonstrate how religious belief offered meaning to life for two patients, Eagle and Alf. Eagle believes that:

“God is everything, there is . . . there is nothing alien. Nothing. It’s all God, right . . . God is the sum total of all there is . . . I am an individualized aspect, manifestation of life force of God.”

Eagle also experiences God through the wind, which acts as a herald, ushering in new spiritual teachings. She says:

“the way becomes clear . . . and . . . I walk down it . . . First there is the wind. Always first there is the wind and then comes everything else.”

However, for Alf, “*spirituality is a feeling of inner peace and serenity within his mind*

and body. He says the feeling is 'of inner peace . . . in my stomach . . . it's just very, very peaceful.' (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 147).

The spiritual need, as a need for God, has also been cited as a spiritual need even though Wilding, Cochrane, and May identify God with other existential aspects such as the need for an understanding of the transcendent (Wilding et al., 2006). The authors, for example, argue that God is central in most people's lives, even for those who are not religious (Wilding et al., 2006). Indeed, the concept of God is closely tied to religious experience, which many scholars agree fosters spirituality.

2.3 Spiritual needs as existential needs

Spirituality is closely connected to existentialism, which essentially deals with the search for finding meaning in life (Koslander & Arvidsson, 2007). One of the most prominent spiritual needs that keep coming up in the articles that I am reviewing here is the necessity to find meaning in life and suffering. A good example of this is presented in the articles by Koslander and Arvidsson (2007), which support the inclusion of fellowship needs in spiritual needs experienced by mental health care patients. The two articles agree on the idea that a spiritual need occurs when people need to establish good fellowship with other people - those who can understand the stress that comes about due to illness (Koslander & Arvidsson, 2007, p. 601). In one of their studies, the patient states the following about his spiritual need:

"Sometimes when I'm worried I go to the smoking room. There is always someone who is willing to listen. We sit and talk about everything...then in this fellowship everything comes out about how we experience spiritual things" (Koslander & Arvidsson, 2007, p. 601).

For this patient, the satisfaction of his spiritual needs, having a chance to discuss spiritual

matters, in the existential sense, with other patients provides him with the means necessary to not only gain insight on spiritual matters, but also to share their beliefs and problems. This opens the possibility for them to understand, comfort and fellowship with one another.

In addition, one participant in Luboshitzky's (2008) article expressed that there was little hope in finding meaning in life and suffering by regret and looking back to the past. The patient, Eleanor, finds it difficult to accept that her daughter is deceased, since she cannot understand why her daughter had to die. She stated:

"I can't part with her. I think about her at all times. I walk the roads she took and I take the path in which the accident occurred. I goes to talk to her every day at the graveyard. I am trying to understand why this tragedy happened to us. Did she have bad luck? What did she feel? Was she afraid? Did she suffer? . . . Sometimes I think this might be a punishment for something we did. I'm trying to search for reasons. I guess that's my way of seeking control within this horrible helplessness. But what am I in this world? I don't have control over fate. There are no explanations..." (Luboshitzky, 2008, p. 32).

From Eleanor's statement one can deduce that if she could find purpose and meaning in life and suffering through spirituality, it could assist her in the acceptance of her suffering. This would reduce her stress and thus enable the healing process to become efficient. Furthermore, findings presented in this section show that patient experienced the need to establish fellowship with people with similar experiences as a spiritual need (Luboshitzky, 2008). In this sense spiritual need means existential need as I have defined it in chapter 1, section 1.4.

2.4 Spiritual needs seen from a holistic view of life

According to Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009), the concentration on biomedicine in mental health care has led to a neglect of other aspects or dimensions that the

human being encompasses (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 34). According to their analysis, biomedicine has neglected the relational, existential, and religious needs of patients in the treatment process. Therefore, they state that there is a need of incorporating the humanistic concept of man in treatment (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 36). They classify the humanistic concept of the human being in two groups. First, they state that the humanistic concept of the human being characterizes the human individual being as consisting of body, soul and spirit, all of which are integrated into one. Secondly, they state that the humanistic view of man considers an approach to health care, which not only addresses the human biological aspect, but also the human psychosocial, existential and spiritual aspects (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 36).

In this view, Bush and Bruni (2008), Hefti (2011), Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005), and Baldacchino and Draper (2001) agree that spirituality is of immense importance in the treatment of mental illnesses, since biomedicine only looks at the biological aspects and seems to consider spirituality and religion as expression of ill health. Bush and Bruni (2008) state that there is a transformed significance in the application of spirituality in the treatment process, so as to increase the holistic outlook of health care. Bush and Bruni, for example, argue that a positive correlation exists between people's religiosity or existential experience, as the experience of meaning and their health. The satisfaction of existential and religious need is often applied as a way of coping with illness.

Research on the role of spirituality in health care may offer a chance of filling the gaps between the satisfaction of patients' spiritual need and the overall wellbeing of patients, as well as reveal shortcomings that exist in the knowledge pool within this field (Hefti, 2011; Galek, Flannelly, and Galek, 2005; Baldacchino & Draper, 2001).

The effect of spirituality in mental health care can be either direct or indirect. Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg state that “it is likely that religious activities may have a direct effect on the activity of natural killer cells, as well as on resistance to cancer progression” (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 37), which is a direct impact of using spiritual activities for bio-psycho-social wellbeing. Thus, spirituality can have a positive effect on human immunology and by this way influence health positively, including mental health. (For the connection between religious experience and immunology, see Koenig, H. G. (2002, p. 11f)).

Regarding the indirect effect of spirituality, their article claims that there is a need of taking into consideration all human rights in the treatment process. It is according to their understanding that health is internationally recognized as an ethical value that needs to be defended and protected as well as promoted by all United Nations member states. For this to be possible, the above mentioned scholars argue that there should be a *holistic* approach to the treatment process, which has the possibility to incorporate the biological and the spiritual aspect in treatment (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 37). This might make it possible for the patients to get adequate help in satisfying all their needs, including the spiritual ones.

According to philosophical anthroposophy and theology, human beings are said to be composed of three dimensions: physical, mental and spiritual. Biomedicine seems to have neglected the needs of existential, spiritual and human psychosocial needs (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 34). Then for the field of biomedicine to take these needs seriously, the biomedical notion of sickness and health should be under holistic and humanistic concepts. To define the framework according to Hefti, “this holistic and integrative framework is a useful tool to understand how religion and spirituality influence mental as well as physical health” (Hefti, 2011, p. 612).

2.5 Concluding remark

As cited at the beginning of the thesis, Chapter 2 focuses on answering research question number one (see section 1.4.1). I found various illustrations and arguments concerning the patients' experience of spiritual needs as existential needs, as religious needs, and spiritual needs seen from a holistic view of life. These are three kinds of spiritual needs experienced by patients, according to the 10 articles reviewed in this essay. For example, Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009) argue that patients in mental health care experience despair, guilt, sin, and the need for purpose, fellowship and meaning as their spiritual needs.

To summarize, we can say that some patients experience spiritual needs as religious needs, some experience spiritual need in the existential sense, and some patients experience spiritual needs in a holistic sense, which includes both the existential and religious needs, as exemplified in this chapter.

In the next chapter, I shall attempt to answer my research question No. 2.

3. CHAPTER THREE: How do patients experience the relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health?

3.1 Introductory remark

The purpose of this chapter is to answer my research question No. 2 (see section 1.4.2), and in order to sufficiently fulfill the set purpose, this chapter has been divided into the following subsections: (3.2) Spirituality as a coping strategy in mental health care, (3.3) The impact of spirituality on patients' mental health experience, (3.4) The impact of satisfying patients' spiritual needs on patients' relationship with caregivers.

3.2 Spirituality as a coping strategy in mental health care

In this section, I shall answer the research question No. 2 by showing the experience that emanates from the application of spiritual coping strategies in mental health care. In identifying these coping strategies in the ten selected articles for this Master's Essay, this section gives insight into how patients use spirituality as a coping strategy to find meaning in their illness/suffering caused by illness.

Coping, according to Baldacchino and Draper (2001), entails a person's dynamic cognitive and behavioral determinations to identify precise internal and external strains that are perceived as excessively demanding or beyond the person's resources (Baldacchino & Draper, p. 835). The first mode of coping with mental illness is to come up with ways of identifying the kind of stressors afflicting the individual and finding the meaning of these stressors in the individual's wellbeing (whether it is intimidating or thought-provoking). Examples of stressors that can be tough provoking or intimidation stressors occur when individuals face terminal or life-threatening disease. Based on the first evaluation, the patients decide whether the coping

resources and choices available are adequate to manage with the situation or not (Baldacchino & Draper, p. 835).

Baldacchino and Draper's (2001) article describes several coping strategies used by patients, with the central theme in coping being the management of stressors. Efforts to manage stressors involve many coping strategies including information search, direct action, and inhibition of action. Baldacchino's and Draper's above mentioned article defines direct action as a way of managing stress through the application of spiritual strategies such as meditation. Baldacchino and Draper (2001) identify 'inward turning' as a spiritual coping strategy that can assist patients to understand the difficulty of their inner self as a spiritual need for relationship with others for sustenance and security; relationship with God through self-transcendence (which entails going beyond oneself to reach a higher power); and self-completeness (Baldacchino & Draper, p. 835). It is therefore believed that spiritual coping approaches may help patients to find meaning and purpose in illness, resulting in self-empowerment to manage their current stress until adaptation is achieved.

Hefti (2011) also states that another coping strategy involves fulfilling the patients' spiritual needs by incorporating religion into everyday activity. Religious and spiritual coping has the advantage of increasing spiritual knowledge, thus increasing the patient's knowledge of existential questions (e.g., meaning of life) and the transcendent (e.g., quest for God). For most of patients in mental health care, religious or spiritual coping is a vital part of their coping behavior. Religion is said to provide patients with a framework to cope with disease-related struggles (Hefti, 2011). For example, one of the patients who participated in Hefti's study stated that:

“By getting spiritual support: 'in the very dark moments, when I felt totally lost and

abandoned by God, I couldn't cope with my situation anymore. I couldn't fight negative thoughts about the future and myself. I needed somebody from outside to tell me that these are lies, that I am not abandoned either by God or by my family, that I am not worthless but loved" (Hefti, 2011, p. 615).

Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009) also assert that religious coping is an important factor in the recovery process and that patients experience a positive connection between religiosity or spirituality and their ability to cope with mental illness (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 36). Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg further state that there is positive feedback from the use of certain religious coping strategies including rituals, prayer, spiritual music, and meditation, which are helpful in alleviating mental distress (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 38). Their article also cites that spiritual and social support work together in providing coping strategies for patients as they allow contact and communication between patients and member's from the patient's church which are important in helping patients to regain hope.

Meanwhile, Bush and Bruni (2008) define spiritual experience as an institutional affiliation, rituals, adopted behaviors or beliefs that are guided by a community of faith or religious denomination. In their view, religious involvement is based on concepts including intrinsic religiosity, religious coping, religious support, and religious attendance, which function as psychological resources for coping with trauma and stress (Bush & Bruni, 2008). Regarding the indirect effect of spirituality, Bush and Bruni claim that there should be a holistic approach to the treatment process, which has the possibility to incorporate the biological and the spiritual aspect in treatment. This might make it possible for the patients to get adequate help in satisfying all their needs, including the spiritual ones (Bush & Bruni, 2008).

According to Baldacchino and Draper (2001), the patients' spiritual coping strategies consist of prayer (84%); religious objects, music, TV/radio (64%); reading Bible (56%); going to church (52%) and asking for communion (32%). The article notes that “through prayer and other rituals such as fellowship with other believers, patients feel the power of God and adopt that power in the fighting against mental diseases and in overcoming loneliness” (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001, p. 837). However, Baldacchino and Draper (2001) maintain that religion-orientated patients consider religion as an ultimate end in itself; it is a principal motive in life and assists well in coping with stress. For such person, religious beliefs and values such as humility and compassion are internalized “without reservation, and other needs and goals are accommodated, reorganized, and brought in harmony with these religious beliefs and values” (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001, p. 836). The authors point out that religious orientation “floods the whole life with motivation and meaning”. Baldacchino and Draper’s (2001) study further examined the relationship between the experience of transcendent meaning, religious positioning, coping and managing disease. Baldacchino and Draper (2001) used a sample of 44 adult patients, 26 with cancer and 18 with non-life threatening illness, with mean age of 42 years. The result shows that transcendent meaning (e.g., the quest for God) was linked to religious activities such as attending church, which presented a significant source of encouragement in patients facing life-threatening sickness.

Fry’s (2000) article generally compares the wellbeing of the elderly in institutionalized care and those residing in communities. Results showed that patients who were residing in community were in a better state of wellbeing than those elderly who were institutionalized. The results also indicate that the institutionalized elderly had a lower sense of personal meaning, a lower meaning of social resources, higher frequencies of negative life events, and more physical

health problems. The study also indicated that patients' participation in religious and spiritual activities was lower among elderly patients residing in care institutions than among those residing in community settings. Nonetheless, institutionalized elderly patients had a lower sense of inner peace than those in community contexts. However, these elderly attached a higher degree of importance to religion and reported to be deriving comfort from religious activities especially in stressful times (Fry, 2000).

These results presented in Fry's (2000) study are important in answering the question of how patients experience the relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health. According to Fry's analysis, institutionalized elderly patients experienced more health problems partly because of their reduced religious and spiritual involvement. These elderly also reported a lower sense of peace, which, as my research shows, may come from having many unanswered existential questions that leave the individual with little in terms of spiritual knowledge (Galek, Flannelly, and Galek, 2005, p. 3).

Against the above analysis, there are two main points that arise here with regards to the research question No. 2. First, there seems to be a relationship between the satisfaction of spiritual or religious needs and the improvement of patient's mental health. Secondly, the participation in religious activities is important for the satisfaction of patients' spiritual needs such as experiencing the sense of inner peace, and religious involvements and spirituality influence how patients experience bio-psycho-social wellbeing. From this point of view, the above analysis establishes that by using religious and spiritual coping strategies, patients can cope with stressful situations and life crises.

3.3 The impact of spirituality on patients' mental health experience

In this section I analyze how spirituality experienced by the patients improves their mental

health. Hefti (2011) conducted a study with 115 outpatients with psychotic illnesses in psychiatric outpatient facilities and found out that patients experienced religion as a spiritual resource that had a positive impact on their mental health. Hefti states that:

“Patients also reported that religion lessened (54%) or increased (10%) psychotic and general symptoms. Religion was found to increase social integration (28%), although on occasion led to social isolation (3%). It reduced (33%) or increased (10%) the risk of suicide attempts, reduced (14%) or increased (3%) substance use, and fostered adherence to (16%) or was in opposition to (15%) psychiatric treatment” (Hefti, 2011, p. 614).

As seen in Hefti’s study, religion has both positive and negative impacts on patients’ mental health. However, it is necessary to pinpoint that the advantages of religion outweighs its failures. On this premise it can be said that religious belief, as a spiritual experience of patients, is significantly beneficial in the improvement of patients’ mental health.

Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005) in their study indicate that meaning in life (which the researchers associate with religion and existential experience) helps patients to experience a stronger sense of purpose and reduced stress levels. Meaning in/of life has also been reported to have an inverse relationship with anxiety in undergraduates, patients, and community samples in an article written by Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005, p. 3). The authors showed that the belief that life has meaning and purpose is inversely related to psychological distresses by showing the beneficial impacts of such beliefs on symptoms of obsessive – compulsive disorder. Galek, Flannelly, and Galek, therefore, argued that the belief that life lacks meaning and purpose can be directly related to psychological distress, and affirm that daily fluctuations in patients’ experience of meaning are associated with patients’ poor psychological wellbeing in mental health.

Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006) interviewed a patient (Alf) experiencing mental

illness, who argues that:

“A lot of people that get sick (. . .) get mixed up between religion and spirituality . . . and they can become quite obsessed about some of the religious stuff in the Bible (. . .) and the workers are a little bit reluctant . . . to actually even broach the subject” (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 148).

The authors acknowledged that Alf has found the experience of spirituality to be very helpful in his recovery from mental illness, but states that mental health workers are very reluctant to discuss spirituality as a “solutogenetic” resource with clients (Wilding et al., 2006)

Meanwhile, Fry’s (2000) tables of the results from regression analyze the findings from community-residing elders. Participants in the Time 1 sample of a longitudinal project that compared changes in purpose for living and future goals for community-residing and institutional care adults aged 60 to 90 show the following relationship between the experience of meaning and spirituality in existential sense and religiosity:

“The addition of the seven existential variables in Step 3 of the study resulted in a large significant increase in the variance accounted for (27%). Personal meaning and comfort derived from religion emerged as potent predictors (beta=0.36, $p<0.01$; beta=0.38, $p<0.01$, respectively). Additionally, high accessibility to ministerial, pastoral and synagogue resources and religious support made a remarkable, significant contribution to the variance accounted for in psychological well-being of institutional elders (beta=0.45, $p<0.001$). The contribution of importance of religion (beta=0.22, $p<0.05$) was also significant” (Fry, 2000, p. 383).

As noted by Fry, participation in religious activity acted as a source of comfort derived from religion and experiencing a higher accessibility to religious support services and resources.

The results of Fry's research showed that spirituality accounted for psychological wellbeing of patients, which is an important indication of its positive impact on patients' mental health.

In addition, Wilding, Muir-Cochrane, and May (2006) believe that patients' spiritual experience can hinder them from committing suicide, and that it can promote patients' mental health as well as provide health workers with strong reasons to consider clients' spirituality as a routine aspect of healthcare provision. Patients' spirituality has also been found to provide life-sustaining meaning to patients' lives, and spirituality has helped them to cope better with living with mental illness. Therefore, mental health care based on purely biomedicine unaccompanied with other treatment knowledge has been seen as fragmentary and reductionist because it neglects the value and role of spirituality in health care, while holistic care has been qualified as a "quality sign" for good mental care (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 34). Holistic care is open to spiritual experience and provides means to satisfy patients' spiritual needs.

Hefti (2011) studied one religious group at the Hollywood Mental Health Center in Los Angeles. The researcher conducted an intervening research to help patients understand their problems from a spiritual perspective, to gain a greater sense of hope, to emotionally forgive people for their wrongs (in order to heal past pain), to accept responsibility for their own actions and to experience and affirm their sense of identity and self-worth as well as to help them connect to their faith communities. Hefti (2011) reported the following findings:

"All 20 participants (100%) in the spirituality group achieved their treatment goals, compared to 16 out of 28 people (57%) in the non-spirituality group. The difference in goal attainment between the two groups was highly significant ($p = 0.0001$). One participant with a 30-year history of agoraphobia and daily panic attacks shared that she

was able to push away the symptoms by utilizing a combination of prayer and relaxation techniques. Participants as a group stated that sensing God's presence helped to lessen feelings of sadness, calm fears and anxieties, deal with forgiveness and resolve daily problems" (Hefti, 2011).

From Hefti's study it seems to be evident that some patients experience that the satisfaction of their spiritual needs helps in health recovery in mental health. Hefti provides another research focusing on the impact of religiosity on the outcome of psychotherapy. The research was based on an 'inpatient' sample study of 189 patients in psychosomatics, psychiatry and psychotherapy clinics in Langenthal. The summary of the result, as noted by Hefti, shows that: "religiosity and also changes in religiosity play a significant role" in patients' wellbeing: In more details:

"The first step explained 12% of the variance in subjective well-being. The second step explained another 38% of the variance. The standardized regression coefficients demonstrated that religiosity and also changes in religiosity play a significant role in predicting subjective well-being and lowering symptomatic distress" (Hefti, 2011, p. 622).

This quotation shows religious faith as an expression of patients' spiritual need or resources that have positive impacts in the mental health of patients.

3.4 The impacts of satisfying patients' spiritual needs on patients' relationship with caregivers

In this section I shall discuss how the involvement of health professionals in satisfying patients' spiritual needs can influence patients' relationship with caregivers. This is an important topic since caregivers are central to any success that can be achieved in incorporating the spiritual dimension in mental health care. Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006) state that:

"Findings suggest that health professionals may need to be 'more open' to clients'

spiritual experiences, even though the relationship between discussing spirituality and exacerbating spiritually based psychosis remains unresolved. To lessen the 'risks' associated with discussing spirituality, it is recommended that mental health professionals take a wide and inclusive view of what spirituality can be. Remaining mindful of the unique nature of a person's spirituality promotes an attitude of 'discovery' when a health professional enters into a conversation about spirituality with a client. A desire to listen deeply to the client's experience and the meaning that he/she makes of his/her spiritual experiences is also thought to be most helpful" (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 150).

This quotation indicates that the relationship between patients and caregivers has a synergistic effect in bringing positive impact on clients' well-being since it helps caregivers to discover patients' need and how to provide meaning to their suffering and purpose in life which has positive impact on their health.

In caring, spirituality has also been identified as having the capacity to help patients to build confidence in caregivers (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001). According to Baldacchino and Draper (2001), nurses have a significant influence on patients when motivating them to see the need for spiritual resources and its impact on patients' health as well as assisting patients in identifying these resources as a holistic treatment required for health recovery. Baldacchino and Draper (2001) noted that:

"As nurses are present day and night with the patients, they are in a position to safeguard the wholeness and integrity of the patient. Thus nurses can incorporate research findings in their practice to promote the holistic health of patients. This implies that the nurse's role is to include the assessment of the patients' usual spiritual coping strategies, to help

them cope with the new demands of illness” (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001, p. 834).

Baldacchino and Draper believed that nurses’ responsibilities entail finding ways to help patients use spiritual coping strategies. Ross (1996) in Baldacchino and Draper’s article states that *“if nurses are to fulfill their function of promoting health, then spiritual care is a nursing responsibility and not an optional extra”* (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001, p. 838).

Understanding of the significance of spiritual coping strategies in patients’ mental health is important since it allows nurses to assist patients in applying their spiritual coping strategies during their stay in the hospital (Baldacchino & Draper, 2001). Nonetheless, Baldacchino and Draper (2001) contend that, if spirituality produces internal strength that leads to wellness and stimulates positive impact on patients’ mental health, then patients-caregivers’ relational attitude is of paramount importance since patients’ awareness of their spiritual resources is best assimilated through caregivers’ practices in care and tutorials.

3.5 Concluding remarks

Chapter 3 shows that patients in mental health experience a positive relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health. My findings also show using spiritual coping strategies has a positive impact on the relationship between patients in mental health care and caregivers because such strategies allow the satisfaction of the patients’ spiritual needs, which has a positive impact on patients’ mental health. The literature review also reveals that the relationship between caregivers and patients has a significant impact on patients’ spiritual experience, which leads to wellness and improvement of their health. Spirituality produces internal strength for the patient, which leads to wellness and stimulates a positive impact thus helping patients to regain their health.

4. CHAPTER FOUR: How do patients relate their spiritual needs to their experience of the meaning of their life and suffering?

4.1 Introductory remark

The purpose of this chapter is to answer the research question No. 3 of my thesis (see section 1.4.3). Aiming to adequately reach this purpose, this chapter has been divided into the following subsections: (4.2) Patients' experience of the relationship between spirituality and meaning of life, (4.3) Patients' experience of the relationship between spirituality and meaning of suffering, and (4.4) Patients' experience of the importance of meaning of life and suffering in patient's recovery process.

4.2 Patients' experience of the relationship between spirituality and meaning of life

Galek, Flannelly, and Galek state that "religion, more than any other human function, satisfies the need for meaning". Galek, Flannelly, and Galek carried out a study on mental health patients who were adolescents and college students to find out whether church attendance increased students' experience of meaning of life (Galek, 2005, p. 2) or not. Galek, Flannelly, and Galek argued that church members who had a strong belief in God had a stronger belief in meaning of life than those that did not go to church. In explaining these findings, Galek, Flannelly, and Galek stated that religion has a significant impact on individuals' ability to find meaning in life that is derived from the spiritual promise of life after death. In their article, Galek, Flannelly, and Galek found out that many religious patients viewed life in the context of the future salvation, and that such beliefs fostered hope that enabled the experience of meaning and purpose in life (Galek, 2005).

Following the same line of thought, Fry (2000) states that the main goal in life is to find

meaning and purpose in order to transcend the self and find higher existential wellbeing. While quoting Tornstram (1997), Fry states that, “wellbeing is based on meaning and purpose of life and the desire to be transformed along spiritual, existential, and communal associations with a higher entity than oneself” (Fry, 2000, p. 376).

As affirmed by Fry (2000), it is a commonplace among scholars that factors such as mutuality, trust, constant conversation and lasting presence are basic to spiritual experience. Fry states that people need to see potential and a future with possibilities in order to experience meaningfulness in our lives. Fry’s study quotes Frankl (1974, p. 33), who believes that we can find meaning in our lives in three ways: through activity, creativity, and achievement; through the knowledge of values (including happiness, altruism and patriotism); and through our attitude towards pain and suffering (Fry 2000). In order to increase clients' motivation to take part in their everyday life activities, Fry argues that occupational therapists should concern themselves with the first two ways mentioned in line with occupation and its meaning. The third of Frankl’s ways (concerning suffering) is said to be essential in helping occupational therapists to understand that pain and suffering are inevitable in their clients' lives.

Concerning the role of spirituality in health care, Bush and Bruni (2008) point out that existential meaning of life, as well as religiosity and spirituality were better predictors of wellbeing both to institutionalized and community-residing elderly patients. Hefti’s (2011) and Baldacchino and Draper’s (2001) research also indicates that there is a positive relationship between psychological wellbeing and aspects of spirituality that include inner connectedness, purpose and meaning of life among patients in mental health care.

Expounding on the matter, Galek, Flannelly, and Galek investigate if there is any difference in the impact of different religions in providing the meaning of life. The results

showed that there were no significant variations in the perception of meaning of life among different Christian denominations including patients from Catholic, Evangelical Protestant and non-Evangelical Protestant denominations. Flannelly et al., therefore, point out that religion plays a significant role in providing the meaning of life through providing hope even as patients experience difficulties such as illness, suffering and death.

While Galek, Flannelly, and Galek assert that religion offers meaning in life, since it offers answers to existential questions, the authors found out that religiosity helped patients find meaning in life. For example, Wilding, Cochrane, and May report that the patient named Eagle stated that “God was the essence of life, life is the manifestation of the force of God” (Wilding et al., 2006), whereas Flynn used Christian religious beliefs (*life after death*) to find meaning and purpose to achieve satisfaction. According to Wilding et al., Flynn believes that:

“she is supposed to use what she has learned to ‘tell other people . . . that there is . . . a life after death . . . and also there’s a lot more to this world we live in than what we actually see” (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 148).

Fry’s result from a longitudinal project, comparing changes in purpose for living and future goals of community-residing and institutional care adults aged 60 to 90, shows a positive connection between “*spiritual activity*” and “*live purpose*” understood in an existential sense. Fry writes:

“The existential variables, when entered together as a block, accounted for a sizable increase in explained variance (23%). With all other existential variables controlled, personal meaning for life (beta=0.52, p<0.01), participation in spiritual activity and expression (beta=0.46, p<0.01) and sense of inner peace with self (beta=0.36, p<0.01) emerged as the most salient predictors” (Fry, 2000, p. 381).

Fry's (2008) findings indicate that patients tend to find meaning in life through spiritual experiences, regardless of the seriousness of their suffering. Even though there are various ways through which people find meaning and purpose in life, many patients identify religion as being exceptional in providing meaning to the existential difficulties that all persons can experience (Cf. Pargament, 1997; Park, 2005; Wong, 1998).

4.3 Patients' experience of the relationship between spirituality and meaning of suffering

In his study, Luboshitzky (2008) maintains that stressful situations such as illness and traumatic life events are accompanied with intense suffering. Luboshitzky's article claims that such intense suffering often triggers existential questions concerning the meaning of life and suffering that causes lack of interest in life, low motivation and spiritual deprivation. Therefore, according to Luboshitzky, spiritual care is useful in helping patients to find meaning in life and suffering (Luboshitzky, 2008, p. 22-23).

Furthermore, Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009) affirm that the satisfaction of spiritual needs is important in patients recovery process in their quest and search for the meaning of life and suffering, because spirituality enables individuals to understand the meaning of suffering and thus overcome self-pity and the questions of 'why me' that usually come with suffering. One of the participants in Luboshitzky's research (Deegan) who suffers from schizophrenia stated that the satisfaction of her spiritual needs played a huge role in her recovery, because it enabled her to find the meaning of her suffering and overcome helplessness. Quoting Frankl (1985), Luboshitzky concludes that "life does not take shape until it has endured the hammer-blows of fate under the white heat of suffering".

Patients have different perceptions of spirituality, how they feel it and relate it to life meaning. Even so, as cited by Fry (2000), factors such as mutuality, trust, constant conversation

and lasting presence are basic to spiritual experience. Fry states that people need to see *potential* and *a future with possibilities* in order to experience meaningfulness in our lives. Fry's study quotes Frankl, who believes that we can find meaning in our lives in three ways: through activity, creativity, and achievement; through the knowledge of values (including happiness, altruism and patriotism); and through our approach towards pain *and suffering*. In order to increase clients' motivation to take part in their everyday life activities, Fry argues that occupational therapists should concern themselves with the first two ways mentioned in line with occupation and its meaning. The third of Frankl's ways (concerning suffering) is said to be essential in helping occupational therapists to understand that pain and suffering are inevitable in their clients' lives (Fry, 2000).

According to Luboshitzky (2008), the first way in which patients determine meaning in life and suffering is through activity. The author argues that having an activity or a task that engages patients is a good way to help them find meaning of life and suffering since it is a way through which they develop their contact with the spiritual and learn about humanism and serve others. Luboshitzky (2008, p. 31) presents a case where Sara, 68 years old, a female patient diagnosed with major depression, was asked what was interesting and valuable in her life. She said that there is suffering in being lonely and one way to protect oneself against this kind of loneliness is through the experience of spirituality. Sara experienced spirituality by helping other. She stated the following:

“The most valuable occupation in my life today is my volunteer work at the hospital. Three years ago, my husband died. I felt lonely, unworthy, and full of self-pity. No one needed me anymore. A year ago, I volunteered to help hospitalized patients. I started to talk with them, to encourage them. I discovered that helping other people is most

significant. I feel worthy and needed again. I am looking forward to being discharged and returning to "my patients who need me" (Luboshitzky 2008, p. 31).

In her statement, Sara identifies altruism as a personal attribute and ethical value. Altruism is described by Elkins and associates (1988) as a component of spirituality considering her caring attitude towards others while planning her rehabilitation program could possibly enhance her occupational engagement" (Luboshitzky 2008, p. 31). Thus, through her pain and suffering, Sara was able to identify altruism as an important aspect in her life and come up with an activity that motivated her and gave her reason to find meaning and purpose in life, thus reducing her depression and assisting her in the recovery process.

Luboshitzky (2008) also indicates that spirituality helps patients understand their suffering as a chance for changing their way of life or an opportunity to understand the transcendent and find meaning in life. The matter was elaborated in Luboshitzky's interview with Tom (a 45-year-old patient who had been diagnosed with multiple sclerosis (MS)), who described how he relates his belief in God to the meaning of his suffering. Tom stated that:

"Multiple sclerosis is an opportunity to live in the present. I am constantly aware of my muscle cramps and twists. Sometimes it is very frightening, but always exciting. It might seem weird, but I pretty much thank God for sending me MS. I feel that it is the most meaningful experience in my life. Until that time, I used to run from one place to another. I never stopped to ask myself where I was running to and what for. The MS stopped my meaningless race. I am learning to live at a snail's pace. I am watching myself and the world with great patience and attention. In the past, I used to know the world mainly by

doing. Now I experience different ways of knowing, through being and becoming. Despite my limitations, I feel fuller than ever” (Luboshitzky, 2008, p. 31).

The quote shows that Tom was able to explore the purpose of his suffering in relation to the unique meaning of his life because of his religious faith. Tom realizes that the search for meaning is an individual task which each person must do alone, and he understood that even though one is not always able to change the situation, one can always change the attitude towards it (Luboshitzky, 2008). In Wilding et al.’s (2006) study, a patient named Flynn believed that her illness meant suffering, and pain motivated her to search for spiritual healing when she thought about healing as follows:

“I was so ill . . . I became interested in healing . . . It’s like hanging on to the end of a cliff you’ve got nothing else . . . You know the doctors can’t help you . . . and ah, you’re sort of desperate . . . and it’s when you’re at your lowest then . . . I looked at myself. I was in so much pain. I thought, is this all there is to life? . . . well if I hadn’t got mental I wouldn’t have got spiritual . . . a lot of people do reach some sort of crisis in their life . . . which makes them search for other things outside of themselves” (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 147).

Wilding, Cochrane, and May point out how a person’s illness may put the person in a position or need to search after spirituality or religion:

“Flynn’s experience was a little different as she had no early experiences of religion or spirituality. Flynn’s spiritual journey began unexpectedly when she developed an illness, which she describes as both physical, in the form of an extremely painful tissue disorder, and also mental, as she experienced emotional distress, anxiety and depression” (Wilding et al., 2006, p. 147).

Flynn, as can be seen from this quotation, was able to find meaning to her sufferings and life when she discovered religious and spiritual values. The satisfaction of her spiritual need was prompted by sufferings encountered in her illness which made her search for meaning.

Luboshitzky states that “self-love obscures self-knowledge by generating illusions about oneself and the creation while genuine love is selfless and can be achieved only out of mindful and individual unrestricted choice” . In relation to this statement, Luboshitzky quotes an anthroposoph Rudolf Steiner who believes that “it is on this claim that the attribution of suffering to modern culture can be focused which extremely values freedom, support, self-control, and autonomy.” Luboshitzky shares Steiner’s opinion that regardless of the need for other people’s help and support, many people choose to stay alone, to be lonely, and get engrossed with their pain and suffering, which, according to Luboshitzky, only promotes their suffering. Luboshitzky (2008) takes a spiritual perspective to argue that it is essential to recognize the need for help and be ready to accept of help to lessen the intensity of suffering that accompanies mental illness (2008, p. 29). Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009) give an example of how patients’ spiritual needs motivated their interaction with other patients as a way to find meaning in their suffering. In an interview, participant 2c said:

“Sometimes when I’m worried I go to the smoking-room. There is always someone who is willing to listen. We sit and talk about everything...then in this fellowship everything comes out about how we experience spiritual things. We have heated discussions that give me a lot to think about and help me keep going” (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2009, p. 601).

It can be seen here that patient 2c experienced suffering in the form of loneliness and worry and he got help from other patients to satisfy his spiritual needs. In situations of illness, disability, and suffering, people occasionally recognize their social desires and make sensible effort to trust other people. On this premise, suffering may help as a social strength, motivating people to reconnect (Steiner, 1982).

4.4 Patients' experience of the importance of meaning of life and suffering in patient's recovery process

As stated in Fry's (2000) study, humans are not just biological, social or psychological beings, but creatures that have extremely thoughtful nature which struggles to go beyond concerns about physiological and other primary needs achieve a greater level of existential wellbeing. Fry conceptualized logotherapy as a treatment for patients who perceived their lives as being characterized by sufferings as meaninglessness. Logotherapy is based on existentialism and emphasizes the analysis of human existence as a way of answering existential questions like that of meaning (Galek, Flannelly, and Galek, 2005). Logotherapy has three drives in the treatment of individuals who agonize in mental distress. First, individuals who are suffering from mental illness can be cured if they discover the meaning or purpose in their lives and sufferings and at times, they need help in this process (Fry, 2000). Second, patients themselves are endowed with the will to quest for meaning, either in their faith in God or elsewhere. Third, the understanding that life and suffering have meaning accords patients a positive way of looking at life and assists them to boldly accept life, notwithstanding the existence of suffering.

Fry (2000) emphasized that there could be a tremendous significance in examining the relationship between religiosity, spirituality and self-transcendence and the psychological

wellbeing in older patients. As indicated by Fry:

“If a positive relationship is confirmed and the precise dimensions of religiosity and spirituality that predict psychological wellbeing of elders are identified, then such information and knowledge may be useful for a number of reasons” (Fry, 2000, p. 376).

In the above quotation, Fry (2000) anchored his argument on empirical findings that demonstrated that the right use of religious activities and spirituality can help patients, especially old people, to find purpose and meaning in their suffering and lives. Fry maintains this knowledge would improve overall communications between health professionals and elderly patients, which occurs as patients experience an improvement in their religious faith, hopefulness and spiritual participation. Fry (2000) also contends that understanding the degree in which elderly individuals use religious and spiritual resources might assist professionals and caregivers to strengthen their use of religious coping strategies to pull them through crisis in life.

However, Koslander and Arvidsson (2007) mention that patients in mental health care also use challenging circumstances such as serious illness and infirmity as an opportunity to find strength. The authors, for instance, described a patient who believed that despite the pain and suffering, engaging in various forms of spirituality has helped in finding meaning in the difficulties. The patient stated that:

“Sometimes when it feels hard and I can’t talk to anyone about my thoughts...I listen to music....read the bible or other books...walk in the forest...think a lot about spirituality, but it usually clears up after a little while” (Koslander & Arvidsson, 2007, p. 601).

This quotation describes how patients find meaning in suffering by engaging themselves in various spiritual or religious activities. In this way, they turn weakness and suffering into strength (Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, & Roxberg, 2006, p. 602).

4.5 Concluding remarks

This chapter indicates that patients in mental health care relate their spiritual needs to their experience of meaning of their life and suffering. This chapter points out that suffering is an unavoidable part of the life of patients in mental health care, and that patients want the satisfaction of particular spiritual needs (including the need for communion with other patients, quest for God, service to others, and so forth) give meaning to their sufferings and life. In addition, I discovered in the reviewed literature that religious and spiritual activities have helped to find meaning to sufferings and lives of patients, which is a great predictor of their psychological wellbeing. The concept of Logotherapy points out that patients suffering from mental illness can be cured if they discover the meaning or purpose in their lives and sufferings. Meanwhile, the review showed that participation in spiritual activities allows patient to experience inner peace, comfort from their religion and have accessibility to religious support. I found out that for patients in mental health care it is important to use religious and spiritual activities to find purpose and meaning, which allows them to withstand the most severe of life's suffering, including death, illness, suffering, and other problems.

5. CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION AND CRITICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE RESULTS

5.1 Introductory remark

In this chapter I shall discuss the findings of my literature review in the light of the theoretical framework (section 1.5) and other relevant studies or scholarly researches. Chapter 5 concludes my study and consists of the following sections: (5.2) Findings, (5.3) Discussion, (5.4) Summary and conclusion, and (5.5) Recommendations and suggestions for further research.

5.2. Findings

The literature review was used to provide answers to the three research questions. Research question No. 1 (see section 1.4.1) of my study was answered in chapter 2. A close evaluation of the ten studies revealed that patients experienced spiritual needs as religious needs, as existential needs, and spiritual needs seen from a holistic view of life (which includes cases where patients experienced spiritual needs as both existential and religious needs). For example, a review of the Frankl (2007) showed that spirituality is closely connected to existentialism while the needs for inner peace and transcendence emerged among spiritual needs within this category. Similarly, the findings of my study are in line with Frankl's concept of logotherapy, which argues that answering existential questions augments patients' psychological wellbeing. Fry argued that patients who perceive life as being meaningful and those who are in close communion with God had better chances of having a positive outlook towards life, which keeps them from the vulnerability of depression (see section 2.2). Frankl also discusses another spiritual need such as the need for fellowship with other people, especially those who can understand the stress that comes about due to illness. The chapter shows the spiritual need as the religious need for God, where the concept of God is closely tied to the experience of religion, such as participation in

religious activities and the pursuit of God (see section 2.2). Chapter 2 concludes by showing spiritual needs from a holistic view of life (see section 2.4) which is in line with the salutogenic model as described by Antonovsky (2012) and Hanson (2007) (see section 1.5). Chapter 3 of my study deals with research question No. 2, namely: “How patients experience the relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health.” My findings show that the impact of religion is partly positive and partly negative on the mental health of patients, though the proportion of its success outweighs its failure. On this premise, it can be said that religious belief as a spiritual experience of patients is significantly good for health (section 3.3). The section shows that some patients experienced spirituality as a coping strategy while others associated spirituality with the improvement of their mental health. As I have pointed out in chapter 2, Frankl (2007), for example, argues that the satisfaction of patients’ religious and existential needs helped patients to find meaning in their illness and suffering, thereby enabling them to manage or cope with the situation. Hefti (2011) also argues that patients’ religiosity improved their transcendence and existential knowledge, thereby enabling them to utilize spiritual coping tactics to cope with disease-related struggles (see section 2.2). The review shows that religiosity was likely to impact positively on patients’ mental health (section 2.4). Meanwhile, Antonovsky’s (2012) salutogenic model contends that believing that one’s life lacks meaning and purpose is a sign of psychological distress because regular fluctuations in patients’ experience of meaning are related to patients’ poor psychological wellbeing.

Chapter 3 ends by exploring the impact of satisfying patients’ spiritual needs and patients’ relationship with caregivers, which was founded on the premise that a positive relationship between patients and caregivers is beneficial to patients’ mental health (see section 3.4).

Consequently Hefti's (2011) holistic care model argue that nurses who assisted patients to identify spiritual resources enabled patients to use spiritual coping strategies to improve their mental health whereas fostering beneficial and friendly relationships between caregivers and mental health care patients.

Findings in chapter 4 of my study show that spirituality helped health care patients to experience transcendence and existential meaning of life (section 4.2). The results also agree with Antonovsky's (2012) idea that religiosity, by providing the promise of life after death, helped patients for find hope and meaning in life even as they struggled with their illnesses. On the relationship between spirituality and meaning of suffering, Antonovsky (2012) argued that spirituality enabled patients to understand the meaning of suffering by helping them to overcome the feeling of helplessness. Spiritual, existential experiences such as mutuality, trust, constant conversation and lasting communion were also mentioned to improve patients' engagement in daily activities of life and encouraged them to serve others, which provides an effective strategy for patients to cope with suffering. Furthermore, Frankl (2003) found out that spirituality helped patients to find answers to existential questions that helped them to cope with illnesses and discover meaning or purpose in life. More interestingly, section 4.4 points out that religiosity pulls mental health care patients through suffering, which is supported by Frankl's (2007) findings especially when caregivers enabled the patients to identify important spiritual resources that could give them strength even as they faced pain and difficulties.

5.2.1 Strengths and weaknesses of the method

The use of hermeneutic phenomenology provides a cost effective method of carrying out a study as the methods involved in the collection of data for the study are not resource intensive (Crist & Tanner, 2003). The process also allows the researcher to unearth the hidden meaning of

the experiences from the external environment that would not necessarily be evident if the research did not employ the hermeneutic phenomenology research design (Finfgeld & Johnson, 2013). The process also leads to the identification of a sizable quantity of quality information in regard to the subject matter under study. Given that the method applies secondary data, it is possible for more time to be spent digging deeper into the phenomena under study as the process is already reduced, hence, there is enough time to reflect on the information contained in the sources included in the review.

By employing the hermeneutic phenomenology design, the researcher runs the risk of being biased. The researcher may choose to include the studies that are going to lead to the collection of data that will lead to a specific conclusion (Kafle, 2011). The biasness occurs when the researcher conducts the study in a manner that leads to the advancement of personal proposal. The research design also predisposes the review to the transfer or the duplication of the errors that could have been made in the research articles that are included in the review (Hefti, 2011). In a situation where the researcher is constrained by time, the process could end up being rushed and a result information that is relevant to the phenomena under study being lost in the process (Kafle, 2011; Ajjawi & Higgs, 2007).

5.3 Discussion of the findings

I think that the findings of the current study answer my three research questions. The purpose of this section is to crosscheck the findings of the studies I included in my research and findings of others in order to gauge their coherence or dissimilarity.

The idea that patients in mental health care experience diverse spiritual needs gains support in numerous studies other than the ones reviewed in my research. For instance, Herrman and Jané-Llopis (2012) agree with the notion that mental health care patients experience the need to find

meaning and purpose in life and find the meaning of the transcendent. Similar to my study, Goldman and Grob (2003) believe that spiritual care stands out as an important consideration in mental health care. In support of this, Tse et al. maintain that religion has both direct and indirect benefits in the aetiology, symptomatology, diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of psychiatric disturbances. And, Sodeström and Martinson (1987) argue that lack of spiritual satisfaction can disrupt interpersonal relationships between caregivers and mental health care patients, and that the same can support the generation of psychiatric disorder. WHO (2014) contends that the lack of religious activities symphonizes depression, whereas too much engagement in religious practices may indicate a mental disorder called schizophrenia. Venkatapuram (2013) acknowledges that some religious experiences (such as visions) are often misdiagnosed as a symptom of psychiatric sickness.

Dogar's (2007) affirmation support with what my study presents in chapter 3; section 3.3, where Venkatapuram (2013) found out that religiosity was associated with an increase in psychotic symptoms in other patients. Even so, as Crist and Tanner (2003) stress out, patients' spiritual background, such as religiosity, can help in diagnosing a psychiatric disorder and can, therefore, be beneficially included in psychotherapy.

Similarly, a study by Ogden, Sias, and East Carolina University (2014) supports the findings of the current research by showing that spirituality entails personal engagement in religious activities that help patients to find purpose and meaning in their sufferings and life, which is a great sign of their psychological wellbeing (see chapter 4, section 4.4). Moreover, Flannelly et al. (2015) contend that individuals suffering from mental illness can be cured when they find the meaning or purpose in their lives and sufferings, which arise after the satisfaction of patients' spiritual needs. Similarly, Längle's (2003) study supports the results of the current study

on the idea that spirituality plays an important role in the holistic treatment of patients. It is worth of noting Daaleman, Kuckelman, and Frey (2001) view that the spiritual and existential elements should be included in mental health care. This view supports my finding presented in this essay, chapter 4, section 4.4 about my analysis of the ten selected articles of my literature review.

In answering research question No. 2, it is evident in other studies that patients in mental health care experience a positive relationship between their spiritual needs and their mental health. Like in my findings (see section 3.3), Miller (1999) emphasizes that it is common among mental patients who have experienced full recovery to describe religiosity and the meaning of existential or transcendence as effective means to cope with illnesses. The positive impact of the relationship between patients' spiritual experience and their mental health becomes apparent from Ajjawi and Higgs (2007) perspective, when they argues that a large proportion of patients believe that spirituality has helped them to experience improvements in their psychological health, sense of purpose, meaning of life and general improvement in physical health (see section 3.3). Brown et al. (2014)also state that "pain gives birth to higher consciousness and the way in which consciousness is born out of suffering and pain is well known to everyone" (Brown et al., 2014). Stålsett et al.'s (2010) further show that stressful situations such as illness and traumatic life events bring intense suffering, which brings about a crisis of meaning to individual lives. Events that bring suffering to an individual's life make it hard for the individual to maintain a sense of purpose in their lives. The study shows that lack of meaning in life brings about the lack of interest in life, low motivation, and spiritual deprivation (Stålsett et al. 2010). Stålsett et al. further demonstrate that religion is well placed to offer meaning in life because it offers answers to existential questions, helps in understanding other aspects of life such as fairness and equity and also enables individuals to formulate goals in life (see section 4.2).

Other scientific studies also support my findings reading the relationship between spirituality and patients' mental health. More interesting to note is that Anandarajah and Hight (2001) agree that although the spirituality has a significant potential in restoring the sense of purpose and meaning even as patients undergo suffering that result from mental illness, Gabbard and University of Alabama (2004) point out that most authors do consider spirituality or religion as part of psychiatry. Gabbard and University of Alabama mention that religious beliefs and practices have since been thought to have a pathological significance, and psychiatrists have to accept them in the light of my analysis (see section 3.2. However, Tse et al. (2005) cite a scenario where ancient psychiatrists considered spirituality an indication of mental illness following Jean Charcot and Sigmund Freud's argument that linked neurosis with religion. Even so, findings powerfully suggest that for most patients, spirituality and religion presents resources that enable them to deal with stresses in life, especially those caused by their illness (Rebisz, State University of New York College at Brockport, & Digital Commons @Brockport, 2007). Fagermoen (2006) argues that many psychiatrists today believe that spirituality and religion are important in the welfare of their patients.

My answer to research question No. 3 of this study also gets support from Cook, Powell, and Sims (2009), who takes the perspective of existential psychology to argue that spiritual resources are instrumental in the recovery process of mental health care patients. Similarly, Batthyany and Levinson (2009) and Hanson (2007) contend that spirituality can help patients transform despair and suffering into strength. Supporting these arguments, Rebisz, State University of New York College at Brockport, and Digital Commons @Brockport (2007) argue that enabling patients to answer existential question and guiding them towards relevant religious resources empowers mental health care patients to cope with suffering and gives them control over

their lives, which support their recovery. Among the strategies for coping with mental illness and related sufferings, as proposed by Rebisz, State University of New York College at Brockport, and Digital Commons @Brockport, is the engagement of patients' in spiritual activities that help patients to overcome hopelessness and to answer existential questions that often arise in suffering (see section 4.3).

As mentioned in section 1.6 of my study, the hermeneutic-phenomenology method was used to be able to interpret how mental health care patients experience and view that the satisfaction of their spiritual needs has an impact on their experience of meaning of their lives and their mental health. My analysis is based on a comprehensive review of studies (most of which give spirituality a religious or existential meaning) to explore spirituality as a phenomena that can be given a religious, existential, and holistic meanings.

5.4 Methodological discussion

Hermeneutical and phenomenological interpretations stand as the most adequate methods for exploring the spiritual needs and life of mental care patients (Crist & Tanner, 2003). The hermeneutic-phenomenology was deemed useful for my Master essay as it enabled understanding the researcher, to give a clear interpretation of the mental care patients' experience of their spirituality in the existential sense as well as the religious sense (Crist & Tanner, 2003; Ajjawi & Higgs, 2007). As specified in section 1.6 of my study, the hermeneutic phenomenology philosophy and method were used to interpret the ten articles that were used in my master's thesis. This method was specifically useful in exploring the spiritual needs that they experienced, how they experience the relationship between the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health, and how they related their spiritual needs to their experience of meaning of

life and suffering. As such, the method was found to be useful in defining how mental health care patients experience spiritual needs, how they associate the satisfaction of their spiritual needs and the improvement of their mental health, and the manner in which patients relate the spiritual needs to their experience of the meaning of life and suffering.

As explained in section 1.6.1 of my study, a text interpreter's pre-understanding has a significant effect on the objectivity of his or her interpretation of the text. The fact that I am a spiritual – a Christian believer– might have influenced me in having a positive view of the impact of spirituality on the mental health of patients. The same might have informed my perspective on the relationship between patients and their nurses formed my understanding that influenced my application of the hermeneutic phenomenological method. I, however, avoided the negative effects of my prejudgment by maintaining an objective evaluation of the role of spirituality in mental health care. Nevertheless having a medical background with experience within psychiatry, has helped me to balance my expectations, also allowed my understanding to be corrected as the study proceeded. It is crucial to note that I did not generate the findings of this study through direct interactions with mental health care patients. However, I managed to attain a high level of objectivity in selecting the ten articles since studies were selected based on the relevance of their content to my research problem rather than the coherence between their content and my perspective concerning the role of spirituality in mental health care. I found that being flexible and interpreting texts was an important consideration in avoiding misinterpretation of selected texts (the ten articles). Also a recurrent discussion with my two supervisors helped me to distinguish between my own subjective understanding and interpretation from a reasonable (*rimrlig*) interpretation of the text(my 10 selected articles)

Although preliminary findings mostly associate religiosity and existential knowledge with positive mental health impacts, cases where researchers have associated religiosity with negative implications influenced my review to consider the possibility of both negative and positive effects of spirituality on patients' mental health. Meanwhile, my experience working in mental health care settings informed my view of the essence of spirituality in an existential sense as a precondition for attaining internal peace and a sense of stability, which offer diverse benefits to patients' psychosocial state. Relevant researches were compared with my analysis to secure the scientific validity of my study (Rau, 2004).

The study is based on a small number of data with a qualitative approach which that limits the generalizability of the result of the study.

But results from this study provide an indication of an issue that it is important to move forward on new studies for more scientific research on subject.

5.5 Summary and conclusion

The studies reviewed in this master's study support the notion that mental health care patients experience spiritual needs. Patients have been relating their spiritual needs to religiosity and existential experiences including the pursuit for meaning and purpose of life, higher understanding beyond material things, interpersonal values, faith, hope, relationships and personal wellbeing. In mental health care, the holistic perspective approach views patients from three dimensions: 'body', 'soul' and 'spirit', all of which must be equally observed in the process of treatment. Spirituality helped patients to find meaning and purpose in their sufferings and their lives. In answering research question No. 2, my review shows that the relationship between caregivers and patients has a significant impact on patients' spiritual and existential experience that may lead to wellness and improvement of patients' mental health. However, patients have

reported inadequate caregivers' involvement in assisting patients to experience spirituality to be inadequate in mental health care. Some patients in mental health report that nurses seem to be unwilling and have not been comfortable to talk about spiritual concerns with them. In response to research question No. 3, my review shows that there are few concerns regarding the negative impact of religiosity in the recovery of mental health care patients. However, patients in mental health mostly experienced a positive relationship between the satisfaction of their existential and religious needs and improvement in their mental health. This study emphasizes the importance of the roles of religious and existential care in mental health care. More specifically, the study shows that suffering is an inherent part of the human life and that patients have to come up with spiritual coping strategies that may help them to overcome the concentration on suffering, i.e. overcoming selfishness (by taking a conscious decision to overcome it) and through developing sympathy, kindness, and compassion towards others. Religiosity and finding answer to existential questions assist mental health care patients in discovering their spiritual resources that help them cope with mental health issues and enable them to recover from mental illnesses.

5.6 Recommendations and suggestions for further research

Based on the findings of this study, I recommend that spirituality should be adequately incorporated in the holistic model (bio-psycho-social) as the fourth dimension. As advocated by Swinton (2001), we need to adopt the "bio-psycho-socio-spiritual" model as an ideal guideline to improve the current mental health care model. Additionally, the incorporation of spiritual and existential elements into this model should be given a reflective view such that professional care will be based on holism in line with these dimensions. I propose that the knowledge and importance of spirituality and how it can be used to assist patients should be

introduced in their curriculum in the training and preparation of caregivers that intend to practice in mental health care.

The findings of this thesis also compel me to propose additional empirical studies that will explore how patients' spirituality and spiritual resources can be determined in order to properly identify how caregivers can assist patients to find meaning and purpose in their sufferings and their lives in order to help patients recover from their illness. It is beyond contention that both some health professionals and some mental health care patients demand the inclusion of the spirituality in health care, and this forms the core foundation for future developments in the current field of research.

My study is limited in the sense that it does not explore the particular strategies that caregivers and nurses should use to meet the spiritual and existential needs of mental health care patients. This limitation also presents a research gap that should be filled by future study activities. I recommend, therefore, future studies that will investigate how mental health care patients depend on spirituality in coping and recovery from their illnesses.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: List of included articles

Author/Year	Title	Purpose of study	Methodology
Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009)	Existential and Spiritual Needs in Mental Health Care: An Ethical and Holistic Perspective.	To determine if existential needs and spiritual needs are connected with health care ethics and individuals' mental health and wellbeing.	Qualitative analysis (Literature review).
Bush and Bruni (2008)	Spiritual Care as a Dimension of Holistic Care: A Relational Interpretation	To explore the meaning of spiritual care as described by a group of palliative care professionals	Qualitative analysis (hermeneutic phenomenological approach).
Hefti (2011)	Integrating Religion and Spirituality into Mental Health Care, Psychiatry and Psychotherapy.	To examine how religion and spirituality can be integrated into mental health, psychiatry and psychotherapy.	Qualitative analysis (Integrative review).
Fry (2000)	Religious Involvement, Spirituality and Personal Meaning for	To determine the unique and combined contribution of specific dimensions of religiosity, spirituality and	Quantitative analysis (Step-wise hierarchical regression).

	Life: Existential Predictors of Psychological Wellbeing in Community-Residing and Institutional Care Elders.	personal meaning in life as predictors of wellbeing.	
Baldacchino and Draper (2001)	Spiritual Coping Strategies: A Review of the Nursing Research Literature.	To identify the spiritual coping strategies used by the believers and non-believers followed by implications for holistic nursing care.	Qualitative analysis (Literature review).
Clarke (2010)	Body and Soul in Mental Health Care.	To examine how the model of body, soul and spirit can be used to expand the understanding of spiritual care experience of patients in mental health.	Qualitative analysis (Literature review).
Koslander and Arvidsson (2007)	Patients' Conceptions of How the Spiritual Dimension is	To describe patients' conceptions of how the spiritual dimension is	Qualitative analysis (Phenomenographic)

	Addressed in Mental Health Care: A Qualitative Study.	addressed in mental health care.	
Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006)	Treading Lightly: Spirituality Issues in Mental Health Nursing.	To examine the relationship of spirituality to mental health nursing.	Qualitative analysis (Phenomenology).
Luboshitzky (2008)	Exploring the Spiritual Meaning of Suffering: A Strategy of Self-Help, Recovery, and Hope.	To explore a strategy towards healing and spiritual development for occupational therapy clients from the perspective of the worldwide Anthroposophy movement.	Qualitative analysis (Literature review)
Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005)	Assessing a Patient's Spiritual Needs: A Comprehensive Instrument	To describe the development of a multidimensional instrument designed to assess a patient's spiritual needs	Qualitative analysis (Literature review)

Appendix 2: Critical Appraisal Skills Program (CASP) analysis of the 9 articles included in the review

	Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009)	Bush and Bruni (2008)	Luboshitz ky (2008)	Hefti (2011)	Wilding,, Cochran e, and May (2006)	Koslander & Arvidsson (2007)	Clarke (2010)	Baldac chino and Draper (2001)	Fry (2000)	Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005)
Was the review satisfactory in its information basis with regards to the research question?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Is the publication satisfactory in its delivery of subject matter?	Yes									
Was the authors' research question worthy of research?	Yes									
Does the publication maintain high quality	Yes									

research of the references they have available?										
Does the review provide any overall quantitative results for their publication?	Yes									
Does the review consider all the necessary outcomes of	Yes									

their research/ come up with a satisfactory conclusion?										
Is the information applicable to this research paper?	Yes									
How accurate are the results?	Accurate									
Was this research worth in terms of	Yes									

intellectual insight to the subject matter?										
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Appendix 3: Weaknesses and strengths of the reviewed articles

Article title	Weaknesses	Strengthens
<p>Koslander, Barbosa da Silva, and Roxberg (2009) Existential and Spiritual Needs in Mental Health Care: An Ethical and Holistic Perspective.</p>	<p>Lack of any form of data leaves the article open to criticism due to the gullibility of qualitative articles.</p>	<p>Making use of the integrative literature review for the authors' research, this article provides a good background for making a conclusion on the importance of existential needs in mental health care.</p>
<p>Bush and Bruni (2008) Spiritual Care as a Dimension of Holistic Care: A Relational Interpretation.</p>	<p>The article focuses on the female participants, which limits the applicability of the findings to a general group of mental health care patients.</p>	<p>The use of hermeneutic phenomenological approach for the article gives the conclusion a the meaning of spiritual care as described by a group of palliative care professionals.</p>
<p>Hefti (2011) Integrating Religion and Spirituality into Mental Health Care, Psychiatry and Psychotherapy.</p>	<p>Article successfully answers its research question.</p>	<p>A holistic outlook due to the use of quantitative and qualitative research by the author.</p>
<p>Fry (2000) Religious Involvement, Spirituality and Personal</p>	<p>The article concentrates on the aged and especially those who are community residing,</p>	<p>The assessment into the research question is deep since it is one-sided, providing trustworthy</p>

<p>Meaning for Life: Existential Predictors of Psychological Wellbeing in Community-Residing and Institutional Care Elders.</p>	<p>providing one-sided results.</p>	<p>information.</p>
<p>Baldacchino and Draper (2001) Spiritual Coping Strategies: A Review of the Nursing Research Literature.</p>	<p>Focuses on coping strategies, leaving a gap as to the scope and influence of spiritual needs in mental health care.</p>	<p>Paper provides a good analysis of the coping strategies and their easy application to everyday mental health care.</p>
<p>Clarke (2010) Body and Soul in Mental Health Care.</p>	<p>Focuses on religion, providing an analysis that does not provide major information on spirituality as a whole.</p>	<p>Provides a religious outlook on spirituality and provides coping strategies for both healthcare workers and patients.</p>
<p>Koslander and Arvidsson (2007) Patients' Conceptions of how the Spiritual Dimension is Addressed</p>	<p>Focuses on qualitative research that may make the conclusion biased.</p>	<p>Qualitative study provides a lot of information on how patients in mental health care conceive the addressing of their spiritual needs in their health care.</p>

in Mental Health Care: A Qualitative Study.		
Wilding, Cochrane, and May (2006) Treading Lightly: Spirituality Issues in Mental Health Nursing.	The study focuses on only six individuals, which makes the research quite thin for making a definite conclusion solely based on the outcome.	Provides critical information that gives first hand information on how patients experience and relate their spiritual needs to their mental health.
Luboshitzky (2008) Exploring the Spiritual Meaning of Suffering: A Strategy of Self-Help, Recovery, and Hope.	The article has a quite broad concept that may become hard to understand in looking for straightforward research into spirituality and suffering.	This is a good article to understand suffering, despite the need for careful consideration in drawing conclusions from the article.
Galek, Flannelly, and Galek (2005) Assessing a patient's spiritual needs: A comprehensive instrument	Focuses on qualitative research that may make the conclusion biased.	Qualitative study provides a lot of information to describe the development of a multidimensional instrument designed to assess a patient's spiritual needs.

Appendix 4: Results of the article searches

1. The first search for scientific articles in the electronic databases was done in March 2015, using the combination of keywords ‘spirituality and mental health care’ yielding the following results:

Table 1:

Databases	Pub Med	Ovid	EBSCO	Cochran	APA Psyc Net	Oria
Total	380	91	65	17	33	30

2. A second search conducted on the same day, using the combination of keywords 'patients spiritual need in mental health care' yielded the following results:

Table 2:

Databases	Pub Med	Ovid	EBSCO	Cochrane	APA Psyc Net	Oria
Total	45	57,22	1	80	0	239

3. The third search was done on the same day; using the combination of keywords ‘meaning of life and suffering in mental care’ yielding the following results:

Table Number 3

Databases	Pub Med	Ovid	EBSCO	Cochrane	APA Psyc Net	Oria

Total	49	0	13,46	819	0	59
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4. The fourth search was conducted on the same day with the combination of keywords ‘meaning of life and suffering in mental health,’ yielding the following results:

Table 4:

Databases	Pub Med	Sagepub	Cochrane	APA Psyc Net	BjPsych
Total	146	12,509	17	2	28

5. The fifth search was done the same day, using the keywords combination ‘spiritual need and saluto-genetic need’ and yielded the following results:

Table 5:

Databases	Pub Med	Ovid	EBSCO	Cochrane	APA Psyc Net	Oria
Total	10	0	2	0	0	0

6. The sixth search was done on the same day, using keywords combination ‘the impact of spirituality in mental health care’ and yielded the following results:

Table 6:

Databases	Pub Med	Ovid	EBSCO	Cochrane	APA Psyc Net	Oria
Total	42	57,22	3	11	2	173